

Deliverable

Project Acronym:	VRTogether
Grant Agreement number:	762111
Project Title:	<i>An end-to-end system for the production and delivery of photorealistic social immersive virtual reality experiences</i>

D4.5 - Third example of content

Revision: 0.6

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Delivery date: M37 (September 2020)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 762111		
Dissemination Level		
P	Public	X
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	July 2020	Guillermo Calahorra	TheMo	Creation of document, first draft
0.1	July 2020	Ana Revilla	TheMo	Creation of document, first draft
0.1	July 2020	Ignacio Lacosta	TheMo	Creation of document, first draft
0.2	September 2020	Bart Kevelham	Artanim	Second draft, MoCap session, digital character creation
0.3	September 2020	Guillermo Calahorra	TheMo	Correction of issues, VFX addition
0.3	September 2020	Ana Revilla	TheMo	Correction of issues, VFX addition
0.4	September 2020	Mario Montagud	i2CAT	General revision
0.5	September 2020	Guillermo Calahorra	TheMo	Correction of issues
0.5	September 2020	Ana Revilla	TheMo	Correction of issues
0.6	September 2020	Bart Kevelham	Artanim	Correction of issues

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable describes the production and post-production process for pilot 3, with information on the material created: the real one and the content created digitally. It shows how this third pilot finished the storyline created with the first and the second ones (and available in the deliverables D4.1 and D4.3).

This document shows the creation process of the third pilot: pre-production (concepts, storyboards, script, casting), the shooting in Zaragoza, and the post-production process (scenario creation, editing, lighting, chroma cleaning, etc.). It also shows the production process in Geneva, where Artanim was in charge of the body MoCap and its post-production.

The document also describes all the changes put in place to adapt to Covid-19 situation, and how the consortium had to take this issue into account to come up with a new schedule, strategy and locations to shoot the pilot.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
AI	Artificial intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CGI	Computer-generated imagery
HMD	Head-mounted Display
MoCap	Motion capture
VFX	Visual Effects
VR	Virtual Reality

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of this document

The purpose of this document is to present in a clear and orderly way the content produced for the third pilot of the project, and the involved processes. The presentation is as follows:

1. Description of each created content element:
 - a. Development of the Script and its adaptation to Digital content
 - b. Shooting of the content
 - c. Digital Content Creation: environment, character and objects
 - d. Interactions and users participation
2. Phases of the Content Creation:
 - a. Pre-production: script and design of scenario, interactions and actions
 - b. Production: shooting of both real action and digital content (MoCap)
 - c. Production of digital content
 - d. Post- production: VFX, sound, animations
 - e. Integration and programming
3. Technological progress from the first to the third pilot: Improvements and innovations

The following objectives are intended to be achieved with this deliverable:

- Easy access to the created content
- Clarity in the descriptions
- Generation of a useful guide
- Quick identification of the type of content that may be needed by each partner

1.2. Scope of this document

This document has been generated for internal use among the partners, in such a way that they can access the content. These contents have been created for the correct technological development and for the adequate diffusion of the works carried out within the project.

The scope of this document is public, with allowed access to all those outside the consortium who require it.

1.3. Status of this document

- Complete in terms of content, description and access links.
- Complete in terms of summary content tables.

1.4. Relation with other VR-Together activities

This document illustrates the content delivery for the third pilot and the development of the associated technology. The content, ordered in different formats, users and characteristics, will be used for pilot actions and demos illustrating the third pilot. The importance of developing innovative and high quality content is related to other project work packages, such as WP2, WP3 and WP5 to demonstrate the potential impact of the project outcomes. The content has been developed taking into account the technological and UX leaders, and seeking a clearly exploitative purpose of the project, trying to define use cases and ratifying the technological importance and quality of the content for social VR when presenting it to potential stakeholders and/or festivals.

1.5. Deliverable content

The present deliverable includes a summarized view of the elaboration of content for the third pilot. It shows and illustrates each part of the process, including a breakdown of the rearrangement of the shooting due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The post-production process is also included, step by step, illustrating the most important points.

The three pilots are inter-connected, telling and transmitting a story about a murder. The developed story revolves around the murder of Ms. Armova, a wealthy British socialite, in unknown circumstances. More details about the previously created episodes can be found in D4.1 and D4.3 (<https://vrtogether.eu/project-outcomes/deliverables/>). Figure 1 shows a graphical schedule of the previous pilots.

Figure 1. Infographic and release dates of the pilots

To summarize, the utility of this deliverable is to have a complete and global vision of the work done for the third pilot and to understand how this work has been planned and how it has led us to modify and improve the first ideas for the third pilot. This deliverable sums up and identifies all the contents and their access links. It is also important to point out that the document collects the utilities of each generated file, for an efficient use of it.

2. CONTENT CREATION: PILOT 3

2.1. Introduction

The pilot 1 focused the story around a murder and both of the suspects of it (explained in the deliverable “D4.1 First example of content”). Pilot 2 took place in two different locations: inside the TV set where the show “Hearsay” is recorded and the exterior of the building where Mrs. Armova was killed (explained in the deliverable “D4.3 Second example of content”). This third pilot centers the attention into the investigation around Mrs. Armova’s death.

This is the last episode of the three pilots, where a thriller is told as a means to offer a unique and innovative virtual reality experience. The story behind the three episodes covers the investigation of the murder of Ms. Armova and all the details around it. For this purpose, a script was written and it is located in the section II of the annex. The script written features the following characters:

- SARGE HOFFSTETLER: A police inspector, aged, highly professional and strict rigor. His training and experience in murder cases has made him an excellent profiler. He is able to know in a glance the weaknesses of the suspects and how to respond to the questions to make mistakes and reach the truth.
- ELENA ARMOVA: The victim. She was extremely rich and living in a constant opulent lifestyle. Her friends were close to her because of her social position. Elena appears in the form of an interactive hologram as part of an Artificial Intelligence (AI) software program, that is why she has an active role in the pilot.
- RACHEL TYRELL: Policewoman working in the same department as SARGE. She helps him during the investigation of the murder.
- EVANS: Forensic technician that helps SARGE in the investigation of the murder. He wears a white suit and gloves to protect found evidence.

In this third pilot of the VR-Together project, the story takes place in Elena Armova’s apartment on the day of her death. The users follow Sarge and his team to find clues regarding the murder of the victim. This configuration allows users to be part of the experience, being able to make decisions regarding the story.

This third chapter will also need the cooperation of the users in terms of trying to understand what could happen between Elena Armova and the suspects. Just like in pilot 1 and 2, the experience presented by the VR-Together project allows us to experience the sensation of togetherness in a virtual reality environment. One step beyond, users will be allowed to interact with objects, unlike the previous pilots.

2.2. Work planning

Figure 2 illustrates the time schedule of all the tasks related to the pre-production, production and post-production of the third pilot.

Figure 2. Work planning Gantt for pilot 3 content production

2.3. Summary of the planning and development over time

The third pilot of the VR-Together project is the final act of the story presented and developed with the first and second pilots. Since the story continues from one piece to another, the crime and police theme was the common characteristic between them. For each subsequent pilot, more characters have been included into the plot of the story, increasing as well the technical complexity of the project.

After several meetings with the partners of the consortium, TheMo proposed this final act in the story of the death of Elena Armova including not only new characters, but also a more complex technological structure where users could increase their feeling of togetherness, which is something that has been in mind since the start of the VR-Together project.

One of the objectives of the third pilot was to extend the virtual world with the option to interact with objects, characters and the flow of the experience. This was proposed in the first version of the script, where the characters of the pilot asked users to perform some actions that allowed the story to continue.

In the first pilot, the user was a participant in the show thanks to an elaborated plot. In the second pilot, the users can experience a brand new way of enjoying TV shows, where the environment changes quickly, moving the interest point from one location to another. Even though the captured users cannot interact with objects or the environment, they can see and talk to each other, and as well to the presenter. In this third pilot, all users are also located within the same location, which is Armova's apartment, but the situation changed up a little bit compared to the previous pilots. The mandatory characteristics that the pilot needed were the following:

- The system needed to accept up to 5 end-users (they could be in different rooms and locations)
- In terms of facial expressions, it was needed to see enough details in the end-user and character representations.
- The system needed to be able to produce multi-source immersive content.
- The system needed to be able to deliver a photorealistic live immersive VR environment.
- Users would be able to interact with the characters, by answering questions those characters ask, and as well with the objects that are around them.

To produce this third pilot, it was necessary to take into account both real produced content and digital content. All the characters in this pilot are digitally created, following the same pattern as the real actors, that is why the precision in the creation of these characters needed to be hyper realistic. The space was also thought to be created with a hyper realistic aesthetic. Users, on the other hand, needed to be captured in real time, in order to be able to interact between them at the same time, as they were watching the production.

Since the pre-production and production phases needed real and digital content, the presence of CERTH and Artanim partners were necessary, since they were in charge of the characters generation in 3D and the movement capture of the real actors, in order to apply it to the digital ones.

In the third pilot, since the pre-production phase, work has been carried out with Artanim, CERTH and i2CAT, because it was essential to take into account the processes of MoCap, Character Scanning and the processing of this material, in addition to the traditional shooting with actors and overloading of post production. The consortium aimed at a high visual quality for Pilot 3, and thus the scanning of actors had to be of high quality, hyper-realistic. A commercial 3D photogrammetry solution was considered. Several scan options were considered by the best European providers. The most important issues were head and facial scan, scan processing, body and head scan clean up, modeling and texturing from scan.

In the end, for different reasons, both financial and scheduling constraints made this impractical. In addition, the state of emergency due to the Covid-19 pandemic prevented a close collaboration between partners of different countries in this project, so the chosen subcontractor based in Berlin had to be dispensed with. Various alternatives were considered, and we ultimately settled on a solution where Artanim would carry out the character creation process. This includes the modeling, rigging, animation, processing and clean up of the 3D characters. Different from the initial high-quality scanning process, Artanim proposed to use a process based on Reallusion's Character Creator ecosystem¹, which allows for the creation of realistic 3D characters, based on photographic reference input. The Facial MoCap, the high quality virtual scenario and the integration of 3D assets into Unity have been done by TheMo. In turn, Artanim has taken care of the integration of 3D characters and animations into Unity.

2.3.1. Script

The script was developed by Kathryn Gould, the same professional who developed the script for pilots 1 and 2. It has required different modifications and adaptations to suit various requirements:

- Simplification of actors' actions to remove load in traditional post-production processes and focus on the quality of motion capture and facial MoCap.
- Simplification of the interactions to be carried out to achieve a clear effectiveness of the system, from the capture in real time to the scene synchronization, etc.
- Simplification of user actions, looking for their success and operation, given the complexity of the generated virtual environment.
- Development of the environment and virtual elements in a hyper-realistic way. According to the narrative, the elements need to be: perfectly modeled, illuminated and textured. This will resemble a real environment for the development of action and experience. Visual elements that can not improve the feeling of realism or collaborate with the narrative should be eliminated.

¹ <https://www.reallusion.com/character-creator/>

- Due to changes in the action list because of the pandemic, changes in the script were needed, in order to adapt the interactions of the users within the virtual environment.
- The Covid-19 lockdown and the associated change in the schedule was also a decisive factor in the reduction of the script, since effective working times were shortened due to the lockdown.

This task has been developed in collaboration with Artanim. Ignacio Lacosta and Ana Revilla from TheMo simplified and reduced the original script, while maintaining fidelity to the original, without losing coherence or meaning and keeping a good story. Jonathan Mellor, one of the actors, also collaborated in the rehearsals prior to the shooting, adapting the texts to the possible interactions of the users or players. The different versions of the script are in ANNEX I of this document.

The script is divided into four sequences that helped the technical and artistic crew to differentiate takes and scenarios in order to present a better structured information to the audience. These four sequences include different characters and users:.

1. Sequence 1: including ALL USERS, SARGE, RACHEL, EVANS, and the new character of the story, ELENA. In this first sequence, all users are located in the living room of the victim, ELENA ARMOVA, who is artificially brought to life thanks to an AI system that the police have developed. SARGE, who is leading the investigation, and RACHEL, part of his team, are presented to the audience. At the end of the sequence, half of the users are assigned to follow SARGE, and the other half to follow RACHEL and ELENA.
2. Sequence 2: including SARGE, EVANS and up to three USERS. Both SARGE and EVANS realize that there are more clues than they thought it would be, and that could be significant to make a conclusion of the murder of ELENA.
3. Sequence 3: including RACHEL, ELENA and up to two USERS. RACHEL finds ELENA crying for her assistant and RACHEL finds out they were in love. After finding proof of ELENA's testimony, RACHEL runs to tell SARGE her discovery.
4. Sequence 4: including SARGE, RACHEL and ALL USERS. In the last sequence, both characters deduce what was going on prior the murder of the victim, and SARGE finds out who the murdered is.

Throughout this process, the creation of a **shooting list and a scenario layout** has been very important in order to synchronize the work between the technical team and the content creation team.

2.3.2. Shooting list and objects

The shooting list has allowed us to define relevant actions, how to shoot them, and what objects were essential to use. It has been classified by sequences to facilitate technical work and, of course, acting and directing within the shooting. This document is provided in ANNEX II.

The shooting list (and the script) includes the interaction between the characters (and the users) and with different objects that have different uses in the pilot. Some objects (such as the glass or the forensic brush) are only used by the characters in order to give the piece a more realistic context, but other objects are used in order to trigger different situations. Table 1 summarizes the objects that appear during the development of the story.

OBJECT	WHO USES IT	PURPOSE
Glass	EVANS	Decorative use
Forensic brush	EVANS	Decorative use
Evidence bag	EVANS	Decorative use
Phone	SARGE	The noise produced by the phone finder is stopped when SARGE picks it up and touches it
Frame	RACHEL	It contains the SD card, which triggers an action
SD card	USERS	It triggers an action when is picked up
Notebook	SARGE	Decorative use
Pen	SARGE	Decorative use
Phone finder	USERS	It triggers an action when it is used.
Futuristic device	RACHEL	Decorative use. ELENA comes up from this device when used.
Forensic scan camera	EVANS	Decorative use. Pictures of the suspects come up when used.
Futuristic laptop	EVANS	Decorative use. Pictures of the suspects come up when used.

Table 1. Objects used in the third pilot

2.3.3. Layout and scenario creation

The design and creation of the scenario, implies the use of a scenario layout. The layout, presented in Fig. 4, proposes a first version of the environment where the action is going to take place at. This layout is used to search for references and to test different acting options in it. The structure of the layout was used as a reference for the creation of the Unity scenario, explained in section 2.7, and it was modified according to the artistic vision of the director of the piece. The second version of the layout included representation of the users, locating as well the presence of the characters in every room. For these reasons, it is essential to break down the script, the list of actions, interactions, and therefore the need for rehearsals with the actors.

These actions allow adaptations of the script, always respecting the original (both versions are included in the Annex I). This is a delicate and essential process to obtain high quality and consistent content, which also allows the development of all the elements to provide a VR experience with the best quality possible.

Fig 3. Scenario Layout. First version. January 2020

Fig 4. Scenario Layout. Second version. March 2020

2.3.4. Pre-production process

2.3.4.1. Casting

To maintain the continuity of the previous 2 pilots, the characters that appeared in the first and the second episodes were played by the same actors: SARGE, RACHEL and EVANS. Table 2 summarizes the information about the characters and who played who.

SARGE	RACHEL TYRELL	EVANS
JONATHAN D. MELLOR	ANA REVILLA	GUILLERMO CALAHORRA

Table 2. Characters and actors from previous pilots

There was, though, a new character introduced in this pilot: Elena Armova. During the first week of February, the casting process took place to decide which actress should play her. The following table includes all the possible options that TheMo took into consideration and the final selection. Elena Armova is the murdered Russian billionaire. Her strong and attractive personality makes her a character with the following characteristics, which were required in the casting:

- Elegant
- Beautiful and slim
- Blonde
- Attractive

- Whimsical

Table 3 includes all the possible options that TheMo took into consideration and the final election.

AIDA BALLMANN (CHOSEN)	ALMUDENA LEÓN	ANA BATUECAS
ANNA HASTINGS	BETH COHEN	ELISABETH ANGULO

Table 3. Elena Armova's potential actresses

2.3.4.2. Initial wardrobe

A wardrobe selection was made to dress the character of Elena Armova up. The selection was based on the requirements of the script and the director. We also take into consideration the best option to obtain high quality 3d modeling and texturing results. The following table illustrates some of the slides of the document made to showcase all the possibilities of dresses and clothes for Elena Armova. Armova suits in a tight blue dress.

Table 4. Possible clothes for Elena Armova

The wardrobe of the rest of the characters of Sarge and Rachel was already defined from pilot 1. In fact, this peculiarity has allowed, despite the Covid-19 and not being able to travel to Switzerland to perform the body and facial scan, to have the characters base with which the 3D High Quality Character has been worked. In the case of Evans, a typical forensic suit has been used, making it easier to obtain a hyperrealistic result.

2.3.4.3. Summary of the process

As a general summary, TheMo took care of the following tasks:

- Development of the script
- Contacting with casting companies and selection process
- Casting actors in Madrid
- Searching and selecting professionals for the following tasks:
 - Sound
 - Lighting

- Adapting the already existing software and hardware from Artanim to perform the facial MoCap.
- Script readings and modifications.
- Rehearsals with actors.
- Pre-production of the shooting: required documentation (camera details, recruitment, etc.) and travel organization for the actor crew.

However, and due to the fact that the pandemic situation changed the pre-established plans (detailed in the next section), some schedule plans were revisited due to this situation. The following table summarizes all the details that TheMo had to take into consideration in order to continue with the planned shooting.

PRE-PRODUCTION TASK		
Meeting actors	Explaining the new plan. 2 shootings: 1) MoCap Switzerland (first week of June) 2) Facial + Audio + Acting Spain (Last week of May)	May 12th
Script Reduction	Elimination of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interactions not affecting the concept and the story - Dialogues - Actions of actors 	April 30th - May 4th
Shooting List reduction	According to the script According to the rehearsal According to the acting	April 30th - May 4th May 27th May 28th
Actor rehearsals	No presence	From May 18th
Facial software rehearsal	Checking the software Artanim tutorial Test	Receiving 22 May Tests and tutorial 25-26 May
Layout	Adaptation to the shooting set	May 26th
Actor rehearsal	In Set Studio (Cuarte de Huerva, Spain)	May 27th

Table 5. Summary of the pre-production and production schedule

2.4. User distribution

As explained in section 2.3.3, a layout was created to find the ideal arrangement of visual elements at the apartment where the action was going to take place at. A detailed explanation of how this layout was taken as a reference to visually recreate the apartment in a virtual scenario is located in section 2.7.

As mentioned in section 2.3, the virtual environment where the third pilot of the project was going to take place, needed to accept up to 5 users. The distribution of the users depended on the location of the users during each sequence that is detailed in the script (available in the Annex I). Due to the requirements of the script, 3 different rooms were designed and created: the living room (where the story starts and finishes), the bedroom (only available for half of the users) and the kitchen (available for the rest of the users).

At the beginning of the story, all 5 users are located in the living room, where SARGE, one of the main characters of the pilot, presents the story and the situation to all of them. He explains to the users that someone has been found dead and the users are there in order to help him with the investigation of the crime.

The victim, ELENA, was a wealthy and rich woman, that is why all the users are located in an opulent, big and architectonically avant-garde apartment with plenty of space for all users and the police team to find clues and investigate the scene.

Thanks to an AI software, the users are able to see how ELENA is brought back to life (due to an hologram representation), and the story divides the group of users into two teams to find clues regarding the murder: one team is in charge of the investigation in ELENA's bedroom and the other one finds clues in the kitchen. Eventually, all the five users are brought back together in the living room, where everything started in order to solve the mystery and see who is guilty of the murder of ELENA. Table 6 represents the distribution of users and characters along the different sequences of the pilot and where they are supposed to happen.

S = Sarge
 R = Rachel
 EA = Elena Armova
 EV = Evans
 U1, U2, U3, U4, U5 = Users from 1 to 5

Table 6. User distribution among the rooms

To have a better idea of the final representation of the users within the locations, Fig. 5 shows the real locations where users are going to be located during the scenes. As stated in the previous paragraphs, a detailed description of this process is located in section 2.7.

Fig. 5. Unity bedroom WIP 5 and Unity Living- room and kitchen WIP 2 with draft users

Fig. 6. Final user distribution look (no users / users)

2.5. Professional team

To ensure the best quality for the production of the pilot, TheMo worked with a professional team. These professionals have been working in the audiovisual industry for quite some time, and the quality of the results was guaranteed. Apart from the personnel from TheMo, it was decided to count with different and external professionals that would help us during the shooting of the pilot.

Our curriculum and background within the cinematographic world and the high-quality post-production, for the national and international market, allow us to know the appropriate working pipelines to obtain the highest quality in our work. For this reason, a specialized and rigorous team has been selected. The selection has been determined under parameters of professionalism and quality in the development of the required functions.

As for the working hours, those manifested by law have been respected in each of the areas in which their services are collected. It is important to report that the rules for shooting (as recommended by the Spain Film Commission in their “Good practice guide for safe shootings”² following the recommendations stated in the Ministerial Order of May 9th) have been affected by the Covid 19. The same happened for the work of professional edits that have had to be carried out in private spaces, and not in the XR laboratory that TheModern counts with.

Specifically, the technical team is summarized in the following table:

DIRECTOR	IGNACIO LACOSTA
EXECUTIVE PRODUCER	ANA REVILLA
DIRECTOR ASSISTANT	GUILLERMO CALAHORRA
CAMERA	SIMÓN ARANDA
SOUND TECHNICIAN	FRANCISCO MIGUEL
FACIAL MoCap TECH	IGNACIO LACOSTA

² <http://www.shootinginspain.info/uploads/files/GUÍA%20BUENAS%20PRÁCTICAS%20ÚLTIMA%20VERSIÓN%20SFC.pdf>

POST SUPERVISOR ON SET	
FACIAL MoCap ASSISTANT	SIMÓN ARANDA JR.
CASTING	LEKANTO SL
CASTING PRODUCERS	MARGARITA MANSILLA FERNANDA ZARAGOZA
UNITY DESIGN SCENARIO	JAVIER LÁJARA IGNACIO LACOSTA
3D AND COMPOSITING ARTISTS	CARLOS RUBIO ANABEL VELÁZQUEZ
DESIGN OF INTERACTIONS IN SCRIPT	IGNACIO LACOSTA KATRYN GOULD ANA REVILLA FERNANDO PEREZ BART KEVELHAM CAECILIA CHARBONIER
GRAPHIC DESIGN	SERGIO ZAMARVIDE

Table 7. Professional team for the content production of Pilot 3

2.6. Shooting production: acting and MoCap

The pilot 3 production has been divided into different phases: content creation, generation of this content, and post-production, among other tasks. These phases span from the elements that make up the pilots, to the action of the actors. This is why in the following sections the specific part of content creation is explained, from the creation of the digital content to the real content.

The digital content generation part includes the 3D Scanning capture of the characters for their hyper realistic creation and the scenario creation in 3D. The real content part includes the action MoCap shooting and recording of the real content. In this particular section, the content regarding the actual shooting and the recording of the body and facial MoCap is explained. The creation of the digital content is explained in section 2.7.

2.6.1. Initial planning

Before the Covid pandemic, a two-phase shooting had been planned. The first phase included several rehearsals with the actors in Madrid to define the actions well and to be able to finalize the design of the scenario layout (taking into account the possible and minimal changes, with respect to this point, that may happen in the subsequent shooting). These rehearsals were to be recorded and performed on a set with chroma in order to obtain more information in post-production, if necessary.

During these rehearsals, the interactions between the characters and the users were considered important, since the actors crew in Artanim needed to recreate them step by step. This is why the original characters performed these movements carefully to facilitate the acting in Geneva. During both the rehearsals and the acting in Geneva, it was needed to pay attention to the movements of the actors and to delimit the space of action of the users. The rehearsal was supposed to be useful as well to establish the position of the objects involved in the history of pilot 3.

With this material, the second phase was expected to begin: the MoCap shooting at Artanim's facilities, in Switzerland. We wanted to move a minimum team there to be able to optimally perform this task. Considering the timing, the recorded rehearsals were going to take place during the first week of March and the MoCap shooting a week later.

2.6.1.1. Scheduling changes

Facial MoCap was planned to take place at Artanim's, and it would coincide with the acquisition of reference material for the 3D character creation. Therefore, the first phase was simplified. The rehearsals were recorded and, although a first rehearsal was planned in Spain, a second rehearsal was planned to take place in Switzerland, the day before the MoCap shooting. This was planned for March 18, 19 and 20, 2020.

However, due to the Covid-19 situation, it was impossible for TheMo to leave the country, so the shooting dates were first postponed to April, and then to the first week of May. Since the situation wasn't getting any better, the Consortium decided to cancel this plan and look for different alternatives, re-adapting with the help of Artanim and i2Cat.

The Fig. 6 summarizes all the previous information regarding all of the potential schedule plans, from the first idea of shooting in Berlin until the last one in Zaragoza.

Fig. 7. Overview of the plans pre and post lockdown

Although with an adapted plan, the shooting was maintained in 2 phases. The first phase consisted of shooting the actors' acting, generating their facial MoCap data and recording their audio. With this, the most important thing from a shooting in ideal conditions was obtained: body action references, facial gestures and original sound.

In order to facilitate this solution, Artanim provided TheMo with 3 facial MoCap helmets (as seen in Fig. 7), the appropriate software licenses for Reallusion's iClone to run the facial MoCap recordings and a complete manual detailing the facial MoCap process.

Fig. 8 Helmets created by Artanim to record the facial MoCap

The second phase kept the body MoCap process in Artanim, but in this case with locally hired Swiss replacement actors, with similar physical measurements as the actors hired by TheMo. These second actors had to study and imitate the acting that was recorded in Spain, recreating the exact movements done by the original ones.

The recording was made in Cuarte de Huerva (Zaragoza) on May 27th, as it was at a more advanced stage than Madrid in the de-escalation of the State of Emergency, which allowed shooting in better conditions. Both main actors were asked to move from their original locations to the city. Because of the pandemic situation, the whole set was disinfected and every tool and furniture piece was, as well, cleaned following the established recommendations of the experts.

Alongside with the actor crew, some technical experts were hired to help TheMo in the shooting of the pilot. Specifically, the following technicians were required to perform some tasks:

- Simón Aranda: Cameras
- Francisco Miguel: Sound
- Simón Aranda Jr: Second facial MoCap operator

Table 8 summarizes the tasks performed during the production phase of the pilot with a description of each one.

PRODUCTION TASKS		
Facial MoCap	These tasks included the helmets made by Artanim that were sent to TheMo in order to perform this task. The helmet included a structure to hold an iPhone X in order to record facial expressions. A software was needed to be installed and their use was needed to be learned with several tests before the shooting day.	May 27th
Audio Recording		May 27th
Acting	The proper acting, without the helmets to provide Artanim a clear reference of the movements of the actors.	May 27th
Objects and measures	Some objects were needed to be used in order to make the acting look more realistic. A searching and selection process was essential in order to use the perfect objects in terms of measurements and size. These objects needed to be checked in order to know if they were valid to be recreated in the future. Measures were taken, as well.	May 22nd-27th
Scenario layout redesign	According to the acting	May 28th

Table 8. Production tasks during and after the shooting

2.6.2. Shooting details

The technical specifications about the tools used to shoot the pilot in Zaragoza are summarized in Table 9.

Type of shooting	Interior
Camera #1 used	Panasonic DUC Pro P2
Camera #2 used	Canon 70D
Obturation	Automatic

Camera height	160cm.
File format	1,920 x 1,080 (Full HD / 1080p)
ISO	Automatic

Table 9. Shooting details

Annex II provides more information about the shooting, like the calls for filming and its planning. As we stated previously, the day of the shooting was modified due to the pandemic, and some activities regarding this day were also delayed.

The day was divided into two structured parts: the morning was reserved for a quick script read and rehearsal; and the afternoon was exclusively dedicated to the actual shooting and facial MoCap. Figure 8 shows some pictures of the shooting and the helmets provided by Artanim.

Fig. 9. Facial MoCap shooting and preparation

The helmets weren't the only tool that was needed for the facial MoCap. *Reallusion's Live Face* app³ needed to be downloaded and installed on the iPhone X. This software allowed the capture of concrete facial expressions that would help the recreation of the actors faces and emotions.

The acting using these helmets were exactly the same as the regular one, they didn't have to play "for the camera", because every movement and facial expression needed to be as natural as possible. Figure 9 shows the 3D mesh overlay that appeared on the iPhone when the software was running, indicating that the head and its facial expressions are tracked correctly.

Fig. 10. Facial recognition software

Additionally, there were two different parts of the shooting, the one that was focused on the movements and the acting, and the one that focused on the facial expressions. The second one was important because those facial expressions were going to be used in post-production activities to recreate the characters using different software. To let the actors recreate in the scenes, some furniture pieces were used as props (a sofa, a table and a stool). Everything was shot in the same space, changing the position of the furniture and the structure of the room, using different marks in the floor. The studio has the measures summarized in the Fig. 10.

³ <https://MoCap.reallusion.com/iclone-motion-live-MoCap/iphone-live-face.html>

Fig. 11. Furniture and space disposition. Studio measures

Lastly, some objects used as props were as well utilized to make the scene more realistic and to make the actor crew from Switzerland know what type of movements they needed to do with the specific objects. These objects have been created in CGI (Computer-generated imagery) by the team of TheMo, in a hyper realistic way. Table 9 summarises the type of objects used during the recording of the pilot.

Glass	Forensic brush	Evidence bag	Phone inside bag

Frame	SD Card	Notebook	Pen
Phone finder	Futuristic device	Forensic camera	Futuristic laptop

Table 10. Shooting objects

TheMo recreated the previous objects in 3D, trying to give them a hyper realistic image. They are available in the next section. Fig. 11 includes some pictures taken during the shooting day, where the set and the installations can be appreciated, as well as some of the objects and furniture used during the acting and the facial MoCap shooting.

Fig. 12. Shooting day pictures

The filming day included catering, the statutory rest stops with drinks and snacks, as well as sufficient safety and cleaning material to maintain the conditions required by the Government of Spain to be able to film during the pandemic. All necessary certificates and authorizations were previously obtained for this purpose. The shooting place was disinfected a day before with the adequate tools in order to fulfill the recommendations of the authorities. The following picture shows the device used in order to make sure that the shooting place was clean and covid-19 free.

Fig. 13. Disinfectant device

2.6.2.1. Edition and selection of good takes

All the material was recorded on hard drives for the director to meet with the editor and select the good shots. In this case, the following material should also be selected:

- Good acting shots
- Good shots of Facial MoCap: individual shots

- Good sound shots: post processing to individual selection is necessary, in order to match with the facial ones, noise cleaning, normalizing, etc.

This process lasted a full day. Once done, the next actions were the following:

- Sharing these shots and all the information associated with them (measurements, textures, images taken that can serve as a reference, etc.) with the 3D and 3D Scene generation team at TheMo. From here, Ignacio Lacosta and Javier García-Lájara reorganized the digital scene and its generation. As mentioned before, the actual shooting can have an impact on previous designs. These changes are normally discussed with the technical team in order to finish the process. The modeled objects had an important role during this phase of the production process.
- The 3D modeling works of the objects that have participated in the shooting and are necessary for the narrative are also designated in this phase of the work.
- Sharing the good shots of Acting and Facial MoCap, and all the information associated with them (measurements, textures, images taken that can serve as a reference, etc.), with Artanim.
- Sound post production regarding the actual shooting took a more complex and long process, so it took 2 work days instead of one. However, some final and extra work will need to be done to the final piece. This work is scheduled to be done after the pilot is post-produced.

2.6.3. Artanim's MoCap session

Artanim took care of the motion capture and MoCap data post-processing for Pilot 3. TheMoCap took place in Artanim's MoCap studio, which is a professional capture stage of 15m x 8m x 3.7m, surrounded by 24 Vicon MXT 40S motion capture cameras. Fig. 13 shows the studio where Artanim captured the movement of the actors.

Fig. 14. Artanim's MoCap studio as used for the pilot3 captures

The MoCap preparation and actual shooting took place over 2 days, after which a period of post-processing followed. Table 10 summarizes the production tasks during the MoCap session.

PRODUCTION TASKS		
MoCap preparation	The day before the MoCap recording Artanim’s studio space was set up and marked to lay out the main elements of the virtual apartment within the studio, optimizing for the actors’ likely locations and paths, ensuring the best MoCap quality. Furthermore, several props were collected (or objects with similar dimensions) to give the actors objects to handle, later to be replaced by the virtual props from TheMo.	June 3rd
MoCap recording	MoCap recording took place during a single day. Actors were shown the reference footage by TheMo to rehearse the various roles. Several trial runs were made, and once comfortable with the actions, actual recordings took place. Each recording had the reference footage played in the studio, so the actors could keep in sync with the recordings made in Spain.	June 4th
MoCap post-processing	With the recording sessions in Spain and Switzerland completed, Artanim focused on the lengthy post-production of the MoCap material from both shootings.	June 5th onward

Table 11. Production tasks during and after the shooting

In preparation of the body MoCap session to be executed by Artanim in their studio, several discussions were held with TheMo in preparation of the actual shooting. Upon request, Artanim was provided with an early rough draft of the apartment in which the experience was to take place, in order to have references for all important objects, their dimension and locations. This reference material was then used to set up the MoCap studio with props and markers in their correct locations.

In addition, Artanim used the supplied draft 3D assets to create a VR application which allowed for the pre-visualisation of the various scenes using a VR headset within the MoCap studio. This allowed the actors to see where they were standing within the apartment space, where they would be with respect to potential user positions, and what space and paths they had to walk around in.

The capture day was executed by two professionals on the Artanim team, and two Swiss actors taking on the 4 roles. This limited the group exposure to within the number of people allowed to assemble while pandemic-related measures were active. Table 11 shows the professional team from Artanim that participated in this process.

MoCap Director	Valérie Juillard
MoCap Technician	Caecilia Charbonnier

Actor: Sarge & Evans	Bastien Blanchard
Actor: Rachel & Armova	Marie Fontannaz

Table 12. The various roles involved in the motion capture at Artanim

Artanim received video footage of the recording by TheMo in Spain. Using this, the various sequences were rehearsed with the actors, in particular where it concerns the various movements, the available space, and the locations of potential users of the experience. Fig. 14 shows part of the acting during the MoCap session.

Fig. 15. TheMoCap director instructs the actors on the specifics for the sequence.

During each take the reference footage was played through speakers, so it was audible for the actors, who could then in turn match their performance to that of the original actors. The full body movement of the actors was captured, as well as their finger movements to provide a base recording for the interaction with props.

2.6.4. Artanim's MoCap post-processing

With all captures complete, Artanim started the post-processing of all MoCap data. This involves the merging of the animation data from various sources - in this case the facial and body MoCap - and their fine adjustments to ensure they apply correctly on the created 3D models (the creation process of which is described below).

While in regular circumstances this is already a lengthy process, requiring an expert animator to spend months on a shooting of this length, the circumstances described before are complicating matters. Even though the Swiss actors were selected with care to match their Spanish counterparts closely, differences in their morphology will show up in raw recorded data. Furthermore, where normally data comes from a single take with all actors present, the data in this case came from various actors, spread over various takes in different locations.

While proving to be challenging, Artanim's team made sure to combine all data into a single coherent set of animations, ready to drive the 3D characters as well as any props they interact with, in the Unity-based virtual environment.

2.7. Digital content creation

To complete the creation of content, in addition to shooting, various digital elements are generated in full CGI. The 3D generation of the characters, rigging and animation is developed by Artanim. TheMo is in charge of the 3D generation of the digital environment that integrates into Unity (the apartment) and the objects that were props during the shooting, used by the actors. To create all of the digital content, the professionals from TheMo have used different 3D computer graphic software, such as Maya, Cara VR, Nuke, Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Indesign, Adobe Premiere and Unity, among others. Our main goal is to get the best 3D generated content possible, achieving the best quality possible and, therefore, taking care of the rendering process.

Previously, we must run the layout of the space and the objects to be able to work on the interactions and planning the shooting. The generation of the apartment started before content shooting, due to its investment in development hours. As for the objects, we wait to the completion of the shooting for its generation in 3D, adapting them to the needs of the space, the characters and especially the interactions with them.

2.7.1.1. Objects and props recreation

They are the objects that are manipulated during the acting. Their participation and relevance was defined in the document in Annex III, Shooting list. Its design, definition of volume and size were previously defined in order to determine the importance of acting and the degree of involvement in the actions carried out by actors and in interactions with users. In the task of design de interactions with the objects, we worked together with Artanim, being faithful to the script requirements. The creativity of the shapes, textures, volumes and design of those more futuristic were in charge of TheMo.

TheMo recreated the previous objects in 3D, trying to give them a hyper realistic image. Table 12 shows all of the objects used.

Glass	Forensic brush	Evidence bag	Phone inside bag
Frame	SD Card	Notebook	Pen
Phone finder	Futuristic device	Forensic camera	Futuristic laptop

Table 13. Shooting objects in 3D

Pictures of the objects and their measurements were sent to Artanim in order to let them know how the concept and size of the objects were supposed to be in order to recreate them in their installations for the MoCap sessions. Fig. 15 shows the definition and measurements of the previous objects. This table is essential for the work of our 3D artists, as are the props used in shooting and the selected reference images for textures and generation of those who are more creative.

OBJECT	DEFINITION	MEASURES (Approx.)
Notebook	Spiral notebook. Pages turn from bottom to top. Probably brown.	A6 paper size (105mm x 148 mm)
Evidence bag	Squared transparent bag	21cm x 21cm
PHONE	Iphone 7 max	16cm x 8cm x 0,4 cm
Pen	Regular pen (The easiest for modeling)	15 cm
Phone Finder		5cm x 3,5 x 1 cm
Futuristic device	Square-rectangular-ish object with a button in the middle	20 cm x 30 cm x 8 cm
Whisky glass	Regular glass. Transparent and translucent.	Height: 12 cm Top diameter: 9 cm bottom diameter: 7 cm
Brush	Thin black structure. Long white bristles at the top	16 cm
Camera	Classic and compact digital camera.	12,5 cm x 8,5 cm
Frame	RIBBA FRAME IKEA	26,5 cm x 20,5 cm x 3,5 cm
SD Card	Regular SD Card	32 mm x 24 mm
Futuristic Laptop	Hemispherical volume, with a hole in the middle to introduce the SD card and abotton on the top	22 cm x 7 cm x 5cm
Sofa		Measures here
Stool		Measures here
Table		Measures here
Room		Measures here

Fig. 16. Definition and measures of the used objects

As can be seen in the script, located in Annex I, during one specific scene of the pilot, SARGE and EVANS use the computer to visualize the pictures of the involved characters of the crime night. Using that computer, which was recreated digitally as seen in the previous paragraphs, an animation of the picture of the characters comes up, allowing the users to see each character.

These character's pictures are screens that were created with CGI and some graphic work, adding as well some animations to make them look visually appealing. Fig 16. shows the designed screens.

Fig. 17. Floating screen designs of the suspects (Elena, Christine and Ryan, respectively)

2.7.1.2. Character creation and animation process

While initial plans were to create a virtual clone of the actors through an outsourced body-scanning process, as described before this became impossible in light of the pandemic as well as administrative issues. As an alternative, Artanim proposed to create the models themselves, relying on an improvement in character creation software based on reference photos.

Luckily, content creation solutions have not stopped evolving over the last few years, among which Reallusion's Character Creator (<https://www.reallusion.com/character-creator/>) ecosystem – as well as other tools – which were used to create our 3D characters. Characters created with the tools in this ecosystem are easily animated in real-time 3D engines such as Unity, by motion capture data from the body and hands all the way to facial animation. Given Artanim's intention to use the eco-system for content production anyway - the facial capture relies on it for example - it was decided this would be a good fit for the whole process.

The first step in the process is the collection of as much reference material as possible. In our initial planning, high-quality reference material would be shot at the same time the actors would perform the MoCap in Artanim's studio. However, the COVID-19 pandemic made taking high quality in-studio headshots impossible. Luckily, some of the actors involved were already photographed in Artanim's studio as a part of pilot 1, while others supplied as much reference material as they possibly could. This includes high quality photos of their head from all angles, full body shots, as well as a set of body measurements, so Artanim's artists could make sure their virtual counterparts match their own morphology. Fig. 17 shows some reference photos of Jonathan D. Mellor to recreate his character.

Fig. 18. Reference photos of Jonathan D. Mellor, playing Sarge.

Modern AI approaches have evolved quite significantly in recent years, leading to major advances in image processing in general, and obtaining 3D information from monocular views in particular. These developments find their way into content creation tools such as Character Creator's Headshot AI⁴ plugin used as a basis for our character's heads. Such tools do a commendable job based on a single image from a single view, but the creation of a more correct likeness still involves quite a lot of manual work, taking the generated output as a basis, carefully modifying the obtained 3D mesh to more closely match our actors' morphologies. Fig. 18 shows part of the recreated character of Jonathan D. Mellor (SARGE).

⁴ <https://www.reallusion.com/character-creator/headshot/>

Fig. 19. Left: Output from Character Creator's AI-based head generation from reference photos. Right: The mesh adapted to the actor by Artanim's artists

Based on earlier pilots and discussions with TheMo, garments were created for the characters by Artanim's artists. The 3D bodies, their garments, as well as props such as glasses, badges and guns were subsequently rigged, skinned and combined, turning them into characters ready for animation. Fig 19. shows the body representation of SARGE.

Fig. 20. Texture of skin and clothes of Sarge

Once the characters are created, they go through various iterations. Animation often reveals problems in their skinning caused by the target engine's implementation, and integration into a lit 3D environment will reveal material and texturing issues not visible in default lighting environments. These problems were addressed during the integration process by Artanim's artists. Fig. 20 shows the recreation of all the characters of the pilot.

Fig. 21. An early iteration of the 4 characters in Armova's apartment.

2.7.1.3. Design and generation of environments with Unity: The apartment

In order to obtain a hyper-realistic environment, we expect to photogrammetricize an apartment, to post process it and later to adapt it to Unity. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, we had to plan this in another way: proceeding with a full generation of the apartment in 3D, allocating the necessary hours and resources so that the result was completely real in lighting, textures, shapes, sizes, etc.

This process included the following tasks:

- Updating the project repository from Unity 2018 (which it was the one used for pilot 2 of the project) to Unity 2019.
- Creating a new parallel scene to get a working structure for the new pilot.
- Knowing the proportions and volumes of the assets.
- Modeling, texturing and placing the assets for the bedroom, kitchen and living-room.
- Modeling, texturing and placing the assets for the bathroom (next to the bedroom), corridor, exterior views, holographic panel and each space that appears in the view of the user.
- Lighting tests.
- Size test

The process is long, marking different stages of supervision, done by the director to correct and indicate necessary changes to obtain the result that he expected at the level of quality and content adjusted to the interactions of users, and of course to the script actions.

On June 19, 2020 it was shared with Artanim so they could start integrating the characters and scheduling interactions. During the following week Artanim started with the first tests to give us feedback. Changes have been requested in certain positions of the objects and furniture, unified treatment of lights, and other actions derived from the first integration works.

Showing up next, an evolution of the rooms created in full CGI and integrated in Unity is presented below. TheMo Production team reviewed all the process weekly, generating reports and an internal demo to the director to check the evolution of the space, the behavior of the elements in the space and all the aspects needed to be reviewed to reach the goal.

2.7.1.3.1. CGI environment creation

In March 2020, the entire working pipeline was redesigned and restructured. Ignacio Lacosta carried out an exhaustive search to build the perfect apartment. Many references to develop a unitary space with a similar aesthetic but that would allow the rest of the team to work properly. Simultaneously, and in constant contact with the director, Javier García-Lájara checked the possibilities of the space and the elements selected by Lacosta, seeing its viability in the Unity environment.

Fig. 22. Reference. Apartment design

A work of adaptation of the existing planning, redistribution of hours, and calls with Artanim, was necessary. The uncertainty of the situation regarding the Pandemic during the first weeks forced us to design a plan that was flexible enough, but consolidated at the same time, so that allowed all the work and efforts to be reused if we can go back to the original schedule. In the new planification, there were more hours and more resources, all of them necessary to obtain the same result as in the first one. Therefore, the coordination and supervision of the tasks became a key job for the correct operation of the workflow and to obtain the expected results in terms of quality and operability.

After talking to the consortium and presenting this new plan, the executive producer of TheMo (according to the director) decided to start with the CGI of the bedroom. This allowed us to leave the room open even to a possible photogrammetry and scan if the situation and evolution of the Covid 19 allowed it. The order of generation of the spaces to be performed in full CGI was marked by this requirement and later by the importance of the space in the script of actions and interactions. Therefore, the order was the following: bedroom, living room and kitchen. To build these spaces we rely on the layout previously generated by TheMo and Artanim's contributions to it. These spaces were created in Unity, although later they were modified according to the needs set by the filming, interaction design, etc. Fig 22. shows some pictures of the first week.

Fig. 23. First week looks of the bedroom

- **Bedroom** (and bathroom)

The first room created was the bedroom, as it can be seen in the previous paragraphs. The work included the testing of the first assets and a first distribution test in the bedroom. Different measures were tested to give the room some form prior the texturing and advanced distribution of assets, as well as the lighting direction for the room.

The evolution from one week to another included the modeling of new objects, more furniture and also a complete texturizing process for all of them. We worked on the lighting, an important element for hyperrealistic results, so we added different emission points of a natural lighting direction coming from the window, and other emission points of light like the lamps. We also created a bathroom, in order to extend the size of the room and increase the feeling of space among users. The guidelines for the bathroom were the same as for the bedroom, even though it was a space that users would not enter, but it was important to maintain the uniformity, aesthetics and quality parameters. Fig. 23 shows the Unity scenario during the second week.

Fig. 24. Unity bedroom from the second internal work in progress

It's very important for hyper-realism to work hard and to focus on highlighting each element, and the lighting structure and distribution was altered to give the room a more natural aspect and quality-looking look. Years of experience in the field of VFX for feature films allowed us to test with textures and colors that give us this treatment in a more effective way. The lighting and texturing process is long and intense, as it requires many hours of work. New lighting objects were added (i.e. the lamp hanging from the ceiling) to replace the structure previously created in the same spot. The past structure impoverished the look and quality of the room and was redesigned until it had the desired quality. Fig. 24 shows a more elaborate bedroom in Unity.

Fig. 25. Unity bedroom WIP 3 and WIP 4

TheMo modeled a lot of elements to improve and work on the details that make the difference in quality and vision: a lighting panel behind the bed, a hole in the ceiling where light comes in,

some small tables, various lamps, a new space for the dressing room was created, dressing room carpet, addition of exterior light, etc. Fig. 25 shows one of the final looks of the bedroom with the previous included details.

Fig. 26 Unity bedroom WIP 5

- **Living room:**

The living room is the most important room, since the scene starts and ends in this space. The first sequence is also the longest. In this location the total number of users who participate in the immersive experience always appear. In addition, it must transmit the wealth and the qualities of the assassinated person, Armova. Finally, it is where we say goodbye to the users, and we solve the crime, that is, it is where the end of our exciting story happens. In conclusion, the living-room is the main character, talking about the environment.

We divided the living room into 2 spaces, one more creative, the sofa area, whose design did not affect the action or interactions. The second one, the dining table area, is more important, because Sarge, who leads this sequence, acts on the table where most of the tests and objects that are going to be used in any way during the sequence are placed. Most of the design effects and interactions of the users happen in this part of the apartment. Fig. 26 shows the development of the living room.

Fig. 27 Unity Living-room and Kitchen WIP 2

Following the indications of the director and the creative team, it was decided that an open space would be perfect for the occasion, since it would recreate perfectly the essence of the opulence of the victim's home. The rehearsals conducted in March with the actors were decisive in defining this room. Several calls with Artanim to discuss the distribution of the elements and the script also influenced the decision. We also had Lacosta's references for creating this room. He had indicated that he wanted a large holographic window so that the light and the digital or real views of this luxurious penthouse could be changed. In addition, this technical functionality allowed us to modulate the light to the needs of the integration of interactions with users, and the actions of the actors, facilitating in some way the post-production process of MoCap.

At this point, it was necessary to measure every part of every room to let other partners continue with the integration process. Every piece of furniture was located in their corresponding place, as well as the position of the users. At the same time, objects were being created to be placed in the room, working on their volumes and textures.

Fig. 28. UnityLiving-room and kitchen WIP 3

- Kitchen:

As for the kitchen, volumes were generated, especially paying attention to the central element, since it is where Sarge and Evans carry out their action. It is in this part of the apartment, where a whole sequence takes place with SARGE and EVANS. The kitchen shares some of its space with the living room, since it was desired to create an open environment in order to recreate an opulent environment.

Just like the other rooms, all the decorative objects were being made at the same time as the structure of the room (lamps, auxiliary furniture, tools, etc.). Fig. 28 shows some pictures of the kitchen.

Fig. 29. Kitchen scenario in Unity WIP 4

In this description that we are making, we want to emphasize the development of the process, always thorough and trying to make the modeled elements and the space of a hyper-realistic quality. It is necessary to adapt to the technological demands and those derived from the recorded action, and that is why everything must be flexible to move, grow or shrink. In this case, the small modifications were implemented and the other elements began to be integrated.

The result is very satisfactory, a space practically the same as a real one, capable of transmitting the luxury of the penthouse collected in the script, and large enough to collect actions and interactions. Aesthetics, warmth and functionality goals are achieved.

The lighting has been worked in depth, using VFX post-production techniques from the film industry, to achieve a desired and realistic effect, with a more luminous entrance, an holographic screen window that projects shadows and light over the furniture and objects that have also been added. The kitchen, which is the room next to the living room, was also decorated with the same style of furniture, keeping the same chromatic aspect between them. Textures have been added on the surfaces that make it a real space.

All objects are also already integrated, textured and illuminated. The quality control for them has been exhaustive to achieve that hyper-realistic look, of course achieved. At TheMo, periodic reviews have been made between Lájara, Lacosta and Revilla to achieve these results. The Unity executable was uploaded on June 19th to the project repository and shared with the project members, in order to be tested by Artanim. Therefore, the works of the following weeks will be those of re-adaptation and development to cover those needs asked by Artanim integration.

Fig. 30. Living room scenario WIP 4

2.8. Post-production

The last phase of every audiovisual project is the post-production, where the content is reviewed and different actions regarding animations, VFX or sound effects are done. For this specific pilot, the post-production implies:

- VFX (visual effects) and animations to endorse the actions and to enrich the content. It is about the creation of necessary effects to achieve hyper-realism and higher quality and veracity in the content.
- Sound effects, such as the addition of natural sounds to the environment, mixing every track and checking that the piece has the best possible audio quality.

2.8.1. VFX elaboration and animations

Professionals from TheMo with years of experience in the field of creating and producing VFX for feature films and TV series also commonly apply those techniques and knowledge in digital content for VR experiences.

In the case of completely digital content like this, with animated characters and an environment generated in 3D, it is very important to apply a good methodology and pipeline to achieve the expected results. In this case, the Visual effects should enhance the hyperrealism of the CGI and improve the appearance of the characters and their animations.

In this phase, it was very important to work with Artanim, since they are responsible for the integration, animation of the characters and other aspects in which the VFX can affect in order to offer great quality content. TheMo worked on the pilot development branch (pilot3-develop branch), where the pilot content is located, adding this VFX and animations.

Ignacio Lacosta	VFX supervisor
Ana Revilla	VFX producer
Fernando Pérez	VFX creation and integration
Javier García-Lájara	VFX creation

Table 14. Professionals from TheMo working in the VFX and animations

The VFX needed in this case can be grouped in the following categories: lighting, shading and other VFX with the goal of providing a better hyperrealistic definition of characters and the environment. This section summarizes the actions taken regarding the elaboration of VFX and animations, including pictures to show the process and/or the final look of some effects.

Creating these effects is a very important process to give the scene and the characters a more realistic and defined look. It also helps the viewer to get inside the environment of high quality photorealistic content. For example, we should create a light layer for the characters and dynamic lights only for them. For the ambient occlusion, we made some tests to see how far we can go with character integration, using ambient occlusion maps provided by Artanim for every character in standing position. We have to locate a camera with the name "Camera with Effects" that just has the Post-process Layer linked to the Post Process Volume in the scene. This volume is the one holding the settings for the color correction and any other effects that must be applied to the camera. There is another object, named "Dynamic Lighting", that contains the lights needed for correct character lighting.

The following effects were added, corrected and integrated according to the generated build:

- Texturing of the characters. As it was shown in previous sections, the digitally produced content paid attention to each detail, including the texture of the furniture and the objects around the environment of each scene of the pilot. This detailed attention was also needed for the characters, since there was a lack of texturing in them, particularly

regarding the shading or the impact of light in skin or other elements (hair, clothes, etc).

Fig. 31. Textures addition to the characters. Left: Before. Right: After

- Rigging correction. In the VFX world, rigging consists of the process of taking a static mesh and creating an internal digital skeleton. By doing this, it is created a relationship between the mesh and the skeleton, while adding a set of controls that the VFX professional can use to push and pull the character around. There were some issues regarding this process, and they were fixed.
- Occlusion process. Occlusion is a technique used to calculate how exposed each object is to ambient light from the environment in order to calculate soft shadows in the scene, and giving the objects (in this case, the characters) more volume, making them look more realistic.

Fig. 32. Volume process

- Hologram VFX creation. As stated in the previous sections, the character of Elena Armova is represented by a hologram, since she is not a real alive person. VFXs were required to recreate the aspect of the hologram. Since she also appears from the device that Rachel holds, an apparition effect was also needed.

Fig. 33. Hologram of Elena Armova and apparition effect

- Character shades and illumination. The direction of the light can make shades disappear, and thus the characters would look plane and without any type of volume and definition. Including shades helps the definition and creation of a photorealistic content and a better recreation of the characters.

Fig. 34. Shading effects. Left: Before. Right: After

- General lighting environment: shades and illumination. The direction of the light can make shades disappear, and thus the objects in the space would look plain and without any type of volume and definition. Including shades helps the definition and creation of a photorealistic content, as seen in Fig. 35.

Fig. 35. Illumination changes in the environment. Left: Before. Right: After

- Dynamic and inactive lighting. This effect that reduced the amount of light in the environment was needed for the moment in which the user pushes a button to trigger a reaction from the characters. The floor and the walls light intensity was also modified because of this reason. This part includes changes in the overall lighting, the definition of shades and different changes in order to make the scene fit with the content provided. In the action of pilot 3 we have different actions that change the illumination of the scenario (switch on/off lights). Changes in lighting and some effects are essential in order to make the scene look natural. Also TheMo creates a forest wall to be changed with the interaction of switching on/off the lights, exactly when the action happens.
- Animations in Suspects screens. In one moment of the action, some information about the suspects pops up from the computer. TheMo has created the animation effects for this action. Some sound effects have to be added in order to reach the feeling of pop-up information, and of course, futuristic ways to show all this.

Fig. 36. Animation in Suspect screen pop-up action

2.8.2. Sound post-production

Alongside the VFX, sound post-production is also an important part of every production piece. This process includes, normally, sound design, sound effects, sound editing and audio mixing, among other steps. TheMo trusted professionals with proven experience in the field to continue with this part of the process. Table 14 includes the professionals involved in the sound post-production process.

José Luis Lara	Post-production sound editor
Francisco de Miguel	Voice editor
Ignacio Lacosta	Director and supervisor
Ana Revilla	Executive producer

Table 15. Professionals working

Specifically, for the sound post-production of this pilot, the following tasks were done in order to offer a complete appealing experience, not only visually but also acoustically.

- **Voice editing:** One of the fundamental steps in this process. It includes a cleaning process from the raw files in order to get the best quality possible.
- **Foley addition:** Foleys are the reproduction and addition of common sound effects that are added to films, videos, and other media in post-production to enhance audio quality. In this case, sounds such as the steps that the characters make or the friction of their clothes were added. This effect adds an extra layer of realism to the piece.
- **Environmental noises:** Similar to the previously mentioned effect, these types of noises add a more natural sound to the environment.
- **SFX (special effects) addition:** These sounds are different to the previous one since these are added in, for example, those moments when a device is used (when EVANS touches the screens, the phone that rings, the wall switch, etc).

The edited and post-processed files were sent to Artanim to integrate them into the submitted build of the pilot.

2.9. User interactions and experience integration

This third pilot of VR-Together introduces an element of interactivity with the virtual environment which is not found within the first two pilots. Specific elements in the scenario can be picked up and/or touched to trigger events. And at certain points within the story, the characters ask questions to the users, waiting for a vocal "yes" or "no" answer on which their chosen reply depends. Given the multiplayer aspect of the experience, this means that the full experience needs to be synchronized between all clients to ensure everyone experiences the same story, and perceives the consequences of the actions - or inactions - of other users.

Where the first and second pilot experiences had experience synchronization limited to a single starting point, the third pilot is much more complex. Various synchronization points exist from the starting point of the experience, the recognition of actions taken by users, the division into separate groups to explore different parts of the scenario which play simultaneously, and other key moments.

This approaches the complexity of a multiplayer game, and it is therefore that originally the ideas were explored to either use Unity's built-in peer-to-peer networking or to have a dedicated server run the experience and be in full control. The first idea was dismissed because of Unity's deprecation of their networking implementation, and the fairly unreliable state of their peer-to-peer networking. Proposed solutions to result connection issues stated up front

that an additional latency of a second or more would be introduced when using them. Third party cloud-based implementations could have been an option, but would mean introducing another component into the platform out of our control. And it would also have implied that no fully local setup could be run in places where this makes sense such as conferences, exhibitions or on restricted local networks.

While our experience does have a serious multiplayer aspect, it does not have the same stringent networking requirements as an action game would have. It has several points of synchronization, but not on the order of multiple such moments per frame. In that light discussions were started early on in preparation for the third year to explore the possibility of using the Orchestrator component (see deliverable D2.6) as our communication platform. The platform at the time was already used to assembly users in sessions, and to exchange information with them.

As a result of these discussions and early practical explorations, our partners of Viaccess-Orca and MotionSpell extended the Orchestrator platform and its UMTS (Universal Mobile Telecommunications Service) api to support our use-case. One of the users in a session is given the role of "Master". This user is in charge of the session management and all its events. If new actions need to be started - such as animation sequences or responses to user interactions - it is the Master who will do so. All other clients can only inform the Master of actions they wish to take, which the Master can then grant, or in the case of a data-exchange transfer to the other potentially interested clients. Full details of this Orchestrator extension can be found in deliverable D2.6, with the API described in its section 2.2.7.

2.9.1. Extension of the Orchestrator API

Based on this functionality, with the specific event synchronization requirements of Pilot 3 in mind, Artanim developed a wrapper which makes use of the API somewhat easier for content creators. First of all, the Orchestrator API was extended with a set of generic methods which allowed for a type-based messaging between clients. The Orchestrator API, as originally designed, only allows for the exchange of strings. The developed wrapper improves upon this by allowing for the exchange of typed data, which hidden from the user is given an integer type id and converted into a json-formatted string which is then transmitted using the API. On the receiving end, clients can listen to incoming event data of a specific type by registering a callback to events of that specific type.

```
public class NetworkTrigger: NetworkIdBehaviour
{
    public class NetworkTriggerData : BaseMessage
    {
        public string NetworkBehaviourId;
    }

    public void OnEnable()
    {
        OrchestratorController.Instance.Subscribe<NetworkTriggerData>(OnNetworkTrigger);
    }

    public void SendData()
    {
        OrchestratorController.Instance.SendTypeEventToMaster<NetworkTriggerData>(new NetworkTriggerData{ NetworkBehaviourId = NetworkId});
    }

    void OnNetworkTrigger(NetworkTriggerData data)
    {
        //Do something with the received data here
    }
}
```

Fig. 37. Example of typed message exchange and handling via the Orchestrator

All the synchronization events of the third pilot use this mechanism. Experience developers can freely add types of their own to exchange via the API by registering such types in a dedicated manager as illustrated below. This construct, while initially developed in support for the Pilot 3 experience, has since proven to be useful for general information exchange within the platform.

```
public MessageForwarderManager()
{
    //Map a type to a specific integer ID. IDs can be chosen freely, as long as all clients have the same ID assignments
    AddTypeIdMapping(100, typeof(NetworkPlayer.NetworkPlayerData));
    AddTypeIdMapping(101, typeof(HandController.HandControllerData));
    AddTypeIdMapping(102, typeof(NetworkTrigger.NetworkTriggerData));
    AddTypeIdMapping(103, typeof(SessionPlayersManager.PlayerLocationData));
    AddTypeIdMapping(104, typeof(SessionPlayersManager.PlayerLocationDataRequest));
    AddTypeIdMapping(105, typeof(SessionPlayersManager.PlayerLocationChangeRequest));
    AddTypeIdMapping(106, typeof(HandInteractionManager.HandGrabEvent));
    AddTypeIdMapping(107, typeof(NetworkTransformSyncBehaviour.NetworkTransformSyncData));
    AddTypeIdMapping(108, typeof(Grabbable.RigidbodySyncMessage));
    AddTypeIdMapping(109, typeof(TextChatManager.TextChatDataMessage));
    AddTypeIdMapping(110, typeof(Pilot3ExperienceController.InitCompleteMessage));
    AddTypeIdMapping(111, typeof(KeywordResponseListener.KeywordsResponseData));
    AddTypeIdMapping(112, typeof(PLayerTransformSyncBehaviour.PLayerTransformSyncData));
}
```

Fig. 38. Example of developer-registered types

2.9.2. Core multiplayer experience building blocks

Most of the synchronization mechanisms in Pilot 3 are based on the aforementioned extensions of the Orchestrator API. While a description of the full set of components is perhaps too much, we still want to list some of the key ideas.

First of all there is the notion of automatic *NetworkId* generation. A *NetworkId* is a GUID-based string which uniquely identifies an object or component within a scene. Artanim created a system which allows developers to derive any component which needs a unique and consistently serialized identifier to derive from a base *NetworkIdBehaviour*, ensuring the object will have a unique Id without having to manually create such identifier and avoid duplicates.

One such component which benefits from this system is the *NetworkTrigger*, which allows for a user to state they wish to trigger an event. The event data sent to the client will include the unique identifier, ensuring the right set of actions is triggered on all clients in the experience.

Fig. 39. Example of a NetworkTrigger used to start the Pilot 3 experience

The example above is the trigger used to start the experience on all clients. Triggered by the master, it starts all animations, fades in the cameras for all users, updates the experience state, and makes sure all characters which do have a retargeting setup (see the Characters retargeting section below) are aware of which users are in the experience.

As we will describe in section 2.9.3.1, the main user representations in VR-Together don't include information on the player's skeleton. That is, by default we have no information on the location of the player's head, nor of their hands. This is however information which is required for some of the interactions we wish to support. In order to fill in the gaps, a NetworkPlayer component was developed which captures a player's head and hand positions from the VR HMD and controller tracking information, and synchronizes it to all users in the session.

Fig. 40 Example of a NetworkPlayer

Non-VR user representations are allowed free movement in a scene. This movement however needs to be transmitted to all other clients to ensure a coherently shared experience. In light of this a PlayerTransformSyncBehaviour was developed which at a chosen rate transmits positional player information, and smoothly interpolates this on the receiving side.

Fig. 41 Example of a PlayerTransformSyncBehaviour

2.9.3. Interactions

In support of the third pilot, the Unity client application has been extended to support several explicit and implicit interaction types. In the sections below we describe how users can interact with elements in the virtual environment, how pre-recorded animation is blended with retargeting techniques to acknowledge the presence of users in the scene, and how users can answer questions asked by the virtual characters.

2.9.3.1. Object manipulation

While the VR-Together platform does create user representations based on real-time depth-sensor and RGB data, these data do not include any skeletal information of the user. As such, on the application side, there is no information on where in a given representation the user's head is located, nor where their hands are. This of course also implies there is no information on the hand gestures of users.

Such information is however crucial for interaction with a virtual environment or virtual characters within such an environment. To fill in these gaps, the decision was taken to rely on VR controllers and headset, and to use this information locally for interaction as well as transfer it to other clients within the experience to be able to share these interactions.

Hands are visually represented as transparent elements so as to not interfere unacceptably with a user's representation. They support 3 different gestures: the standard open hands gesture, and two interaction gestures as illustrated below.

Fig. 42 Phone holding the phone finder while the other points at the button

When pressing just the hand trigger, a pointing gesture is made. This is used when pressing on buttons for example. When pressing the hand trigger as well as the primary index finger trigger, a grasping gesture is made. This allows you to pick up objects which allow such interactions.

Hand positions and orientations, as well as the gestures made and possibly the objects held, are shared with all other clients in the experience, so it is clear to all what interactions are happening.

2.9.3.2. Character retargeting

At various points during the experience, users are asked questions or provided with instructions by the virtual characters. While care has been taken during the MoCap process to have the actors look towards the most likely user locations, the varying positions and heights of the users will ultimately mean that by default characters are unlikely to look directly at them.

To mitigate this a retargeting system has been set up. It takes the head positions of users into account - as tracked by their HMD for example - and retargets the character's head animation appropriately to the most relevant nearby user. All of this of course within plausible physical limits.

An illustration of this is given below where in Pilot 3 the character of Sarge instructs a user to flip the light switch he's pointing at. In both user positions Sarge directly looks at the user, overriding the underlying animation data.

Fig. 43 Sarge points at a lightswitch to flip. Animation moves as the player moves around

This retargeting behaviour can be enabled and disabled as appropriate to the experience, and will smoothly blend between the underlying animation and the desired retargeting behaviour.

2.9.3.3. Speech interaction

At various moments within the Pilot 3 experience, the characters ask users for their input with a yes/no question. For example within the bedroom sequence, Rachel asks the users.

"Tell me, yes or no: do you think Armova's new love interest... was Gerard?"

Based on a keyword speech recognizer, responses are listened for on each client, and when a response is detected, said response is transferred to the Master client. Based on the response, one of two alternative sections of dialogue and animation are triggered for all participants. In the above case if a user in the room answers "yes", this triggers

"Yeah... makes sense"

But if instead the user says "no" it triggers

"You sure? Something Zeller said when we brought him in... about pillow talk, makes me wonder."

To avoid the experience grinding to a halt if no experience is recognized - due to the lack of response or unfortunate circumstances such a high level of environment noise - after a time-out the most logical response is selected which would still go well with a non-response.

In the general case outside the scope of the third pilot, the same system can be used to detect input of a variety of keywords or short phrase responses, which can then trigger events as desired, not limited to animation events.

2.9.4. Experience integration

Artanim, based on their development of all the aforementioned components, implemented the flow of the third pilot experience. The experience is automatically started when all clients have confirmed that all their experience data is fully loaded. The appropriate animation sequences are launched simultaneously on all clients on command from the Master, and based on a variety of the user's input, next sequences are started to drive the experience along.

Starting with all users together in the apartment's living room, all users share the same experience. Once this sequence ends, users are then automatically split into two groups, one of which will move towards the kitchen with Sarge and Evans while the other will join Rachel and Armova's virtual representation in the bedroom. While in different rooms, both sequences do play out at the same time, and if users listen carefully, they can hear the activity in the other room as well. When both sequences are complete, all users are transitioned back into the living room again, to conclude the experience.

Artanim implemented all the mechanics to make this happen, from animation state machines and timelines to all the logistics of player management, group creation, object (de)activation and sequence transitioning.

In order to create such a narrative experience with several non-linear twists and turns, the Unity game engine offers two core tools to help us; Animation Controllers and Timelines.

Animation Controllers are a graph-based approach to creating animation sequences and transitions between animation clips. An example of this is provided in the image below for the character of Sarge in the first scene.

Fig. 44 Animation Controller for the character of Sarge in the first scene. Outlined in red is an example of a reminder sequence, while the blue rectangle shows an example of a choice branch.

Every node is an animation clip obtained through motion capture and subsequent post-processing. Every arrow is a transition between clips, actively triggered by the Master client using mechanisms like NetworkTriggers as described earlier. The animation controller makes sure such transitions between clips are smoothly blended, although there is also a fair

amount of manual labor involved for an animator to create clips which blend well in the first place.

The non-linearity of the experience can be found in the topology of the graph. In particular two concepts become clear; reminders and choices. Reminders are animation sequences which are triggered upon inaction of a user. For example at the top of the animation controller graph highlighted in red, in one animation Sarge asks a user to turn on the lights. The subsequent transitions in that sequence happen in case a user does not oblige, in which instance Sarge will remind them they have to turn on the light in order to continue.

Choices are branching paths in the graph. In the example above highlighted in blue, at a moment in time Sarge asks the users a yes or no question. Depending on the given response, Sarge will continue on the branch which is appropriate for the response given. All characters in the experience, as well as several of the animated objects have a controller like this.

To ensure all these individual animation controllers are played appropriately in sync with each other, a higher-level mechanism is needed. And while we do have animation and transitions defined, this does not yet include the appropriate character audio synchronization, nor a variety of triggers and effect sequencing. To achieve this Timelines are used. In the image below, the timeline is shown for a small section of the first scene with Sarge, Rachel and Armova.

Fig. 45 Timeline for a subsection of the first scene.

Timelines are both a higher-level concept than animation controllers in that they correspond to a linear sequence of events for multiple characters, objects and other content, but they are a lower-level concept as well in that they correspond to at most 1 node in an animation controller at the same time.

Highlighted in pink are the triggers responsible for forcing the transition between two animation states in the corresponding animation controller. The waveforms displayed in yellow correspond to the characters' dialog in that particular sequence. And highlighted in blue are signals listened to by various objects to create such effects as the appearance of Elena Armova's hologram, and the enabling of interaction with one of the graspable objects in the scene.

All in all Pilot 3 contains 18 animation controllers and 22 timelines to drive an experience with 4 characters in 3 rooms over 4 scenes.

And given that Pilot 3 is a shared experience, care must be taken to make sure every user sees the same content. In order to achieve this, the Master client via a set of NetworkTriggers makes sure each Timeline gets triggered at the right time for all other users in the experience. The scene hierarchy this results in is illustrated in the figure below.

Fig. 46 Partial scene hierarchy for Pilot 3, highlighting the triggers of the first scene, triggered by the Master client to ensure all players see the same content.

On top of all this a core experience controller, under control from the Master client, maintains the global experience state and ensures all users are correctly transitioned to their respective scenes. Because unique to this experience, where users initially join the experience together and also conclude it as a group, in the middle they are split into two groups, with each group observing a particular part of the police investigation.

Fig. 47 The experience controller for Pilot 3 ensures the experience flow all the time, assigning users to their appropriate scenes in particular when they participants get split up into two groups.

All these building blocks combined, through a complex orchestration of assets created as a part of this pilot, provide a coherent, interactive and compelling experience for the end users.

2.10.Content delivered

The content for this section will be provided in an updated version of the deliverable upon having uploaded the pilot 3 content assets to Zenodo.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The objectives and the summary of this year during the development of the third pilot experience are:

1. Creation of high quality content following the story of the first and second pilots, achieving the following:
 - a. Recording a 6-7 minute story about a police investigation in which different users see themselves in the apartment where the investigation is being developed.
 - b. An avant-garde technology that allows us to visualize ourselves in real time while we watch the story and see others users enjoying the experience at the same time.
 - c. Creation of content and a 3D environment of hyper-realistic quality.
2. Creation of a story that allows the correct visualization of the technology developed and its presentation in different festivals and fairs in the sector. This technology development includes the achievement of real-time elements, scalability goals (up to 5 users) and multi-source contents.

During the third year of the project we managed to continue creating and developing a fictional story that started in the first year with the first pilot. The third pilot continues the story of the murder of Ms. Armova, a wealthy British lady, under unknown circumstances. This time, the users can be part of the investigation of the crime. This pilot concludes the presented story.

Finally, this deliverable had the following objectives:

GENERAL OBJECTIVES

1. To get a broad view of the content generated to support technological development and the different systems developed.
2. To get a broad view of the content generated for the dissemination of the project.
3. To provide an easy and quick identification of each file.
4. To order the files.
5. To help the general evaluation of the second phase of the project.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To showcase all the content recorded for the third pilot of the project.
2. To summarise the concepts of the three pilots.
3. To identify files and the technological development structure.
4. To help the general evaluation of the third pilot and its dissemination.

ANNEX I - SCRIPT

ORIGINAL VERSION OF THE SCRIPT

INT. ARMOVA'S MAYFAIR APARTMENT - LIVING ROOM - DAY

Lights up to find the users inside the meticulously furnished and massive apartment of the late Elena Armova. At the table in the middle of the room find SARGE, cataloguing evidence bags. Various TECHS crisscross the room now and then, searching for delivering evidence.

Sarge looks up from his notes, definitely not happy to see the newcomers.

SARGE

Ah... here we go.

He sets his notebook down and stands.

SARGE (CONT'D)

For the record, I am not on board with this Civilian Oversight Committee. Not only do I have a crime to solve here, now I'm a childminder? Well, don't expect me to change your nappies, all right?

Sarge points to User One.

SARGE (CONT'D)

As long as you're here, make yourself useful and hit that light switch. It's a bit dark in here.

User One turns around to find a rocker switch on the wall. When they press it, the lights in the room change to a calming blue, and soothing, meditative music begins to play.

SARGE (CONT'D)

What the hell...? Turn it off, turn it off.

User One complies.

SARGE (CONT'D)

It's all controlled by computer or something... we haven't been able to gain access. Rich people, eh? Always finding new ways to throw their money away.

Turning to User Two.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Well, how about you put new
batteries in that torch there.

Next to User Two is a table with a flashlight, battery compartment open, and a large battery. User Two can pick up the battery with one hand and the light with the other, and insert the battery into the compartment. Screwing the cap on turns on the beam.

SARGE (CONT'D)

There now. That's better.

A young woman, RACHEL (late 20s - early 30s), intellectual, a bit awkward, enters the room carrying a futuristic-looking device.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, Rachel, there you are.

(turning to the Users)

This is our Technology Officer,
Rachel Long. She's going to set up
this new AI system that's got
everyone in a frenzy. Rachel... the
Civilian Oversight Committee I was
telling you about.

RACHEL

Yes... hello.

She nervously lays the device on the table and begins setting it up.

SARGE

Seems like a lot of nonsense, but
they say since she was such a
public figure, there's enough data
to make it work. If you ask me,
it's good old-fashioned detective
work that will solve this case.

Rachel finishes her final adjustments and flips a switch. A hologram of ELENA ARMOVA blinks into existence.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Well... that's disconcerting.

Elena, appearing confused and disoriented, looks over at the Sarge, and then around at the apartment.

ELENA

What are you all doing in my home?

Sarge and Rachel look at each other. Sarge flashes his badge.

SARGE

We just need to ask you a few questions about last night.

Elena looks around, alarmed.

ELENA

Was there a break-in? Have I been robbed? I have a very sophisticated security system. You control it with that remote you have there... along with everything else in the apartment.

Sarge slides the remote across the table toward User Three.

SARGE

Oh good, maybe the light switch is on there.

ELENA

Just hold down button three for a few seconds, that will reset everything in the room to the default settings.

User Three does so, and the lights come up to normal.

SARGE

Ten million Euros to tell us how to turn the lights on. That's quite the investment.

Rachel stiffens, eager to show off what the technology can really do.

RACHEL

Miss Armova, we were wondering what you could tell us about last night. Elena thinks for a long moment, growing more and more agitated.

ELENA

I... I... don't remember. I... why can't I remember?

SARGE

Just tell us the last thing you do remember then.

ELENA

I... was coming home from a meeting with my board of directors... I was supposed to meet Christine later... Miss Gerard, that is, my assistant. I should call her, she'll be worried...

She starts looking around.

ELENA (CONT'D)

Where's my phone... do you have my phone?

SARGE

We haven't been able to find it. Any idea where you might have left it?

ELENA

I usually set it on the charger when I come home... just over there by the entrance.

The charger is clearly empty.

ELENA (CONT'D)

But I have a phone finder in that drawer there.

She points to a table behind User 4.

ELENA (CONT'D)

If you press the button, it will make the phone alarm. It's a separate unit from the phone, so it works even if the phone's off.

User 4 opens the drawer, removes the remote and presses the button. One of the evidence bags on the table begins to make a really annoying noise. Sarge picks up the bag, and we see a small round button shaped device inside. Sarge presses it, and the noise stops.

SARGE

So that's what that is. Found it in the trash earlier. Seems someone doesn't want us to find your phone, Miss Armova. Can you think of any reason why that might be?

ELENA

No... I don't know...

SARGE

Do you believe that either Miss Gerard or your boyfriend, Mr. Zeller, would have any reason to wish you harm?

ELENA

What? Wish me... no, I mean... I was planning on ending things with Ryan. I do expect him to be quite upset when I tell him.

SARGE

What was it, the drugs, the temper... the industrial espionage?

Elena looks surprised, and a bit offended.

ELENA

No... if you must know. I was involved with someone else. Now Sarge is interested.

SARGE

Oh... and who might that be?

ELENA

None of your business, Officer.

SARGE

A crime's been committed here, "Miss Armova". I'll need to interview this new fella.

Elena maintains a dignified silence. Sarge looks to Rachel, annoyed.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Can't you do something?

RACHEL

Like what?

SARGE

Make her answer.

Rachel shrugs. Sarge shakes his head and steps toward Elena.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Look, Miss... whatever you are. We're trying to solve a murder here.

ELENA
A murder? Whose?

SARGE
Yours, sweetheart. So if you could
just answer my questions--

Elena laughs dismissively.

ELENA
Mine? That's the most ridiculous
thing I've ever heard. I'm standing
right here talking to you.

SARGE
No, a hologram programmed to think
it's Elena Armova is standing here
talking to me, and I don't have
time for the coy games. Tell me who
the other fella was, or I'm turning
you off.

RACHEL
Actually... the procedure for
shutting her down--

SARGE
It. The thing is a machine, Rachel.

RACHEL
Right, but it's a very complex
machine, so...
Rachel's voice trails off as she notices that Elena's
hologram has started to wander away (perhaps add a flicker
here as she gets further away from the projection device?).
She quickly picks up the device and follows Elena.

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Wait, Miss Armova...
She follows Elena into an adjoining room. Sarge
turns to the
group, specifically to address User 5.

SARGE
Well well... how about you. Do you
think we'll get an answer out of
her about her new beau? Yes or no?
--option 1--

USER 5
Yes.

SARGE
Well, you're welcome to try then.

--option 2--

USER 5

No.

SARGE

Me neither. Waste of time, most likely.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)

Either way, I'm headed into the kitchen to do some real police work. Follow me or go with Rachel and her little toy, up to you.

Sarge heads in the opposite direction from the two women. The Users decide which group to follow.

USER GROUP 1 (WITH SARGE) -

INT. ARMOVA'S KITCHEN - DAY

Sarge is already in the kitchen talking with a TECH, who is examining two wine glasses by the sink.

SARGE

Two different shades you say?
That's interesting. What are the chances she changed lipsticks in the middle of the evening?

Sarge looks up to see the USERS who have decided to join him.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, good. Now you'll get to see some real crime-solving. Evans here was just telling me that there are two different shades of lipstick on these wine glasses. Having a drink with her assistant, perhaps?

The Tech (EVANS) is brushing finger-printing dust on the glasses now and looking them over.

EVANS

And... it looks to me like three different sets of fingerprints, actually.

SARGE

Three? Now we're getting somewhere.

Evans takes a picture of each fingerprint, then pulls out the card and puts it on the table.

EVANS

If you could stick that in my laptop there and hit enter, the program is all set up. It'll do the rest.

User 1 goes to the table and inserts the card, presses Enter. The computer screen flashes to an image that says "processing" and some kind of progress bar.

SARGE

Let me guess... Armova, Gerard and Zeller.

The results pop up: "SAMPLE 1: Elena Armova; SAMPLE 2: Christine Gerard; SAMPLE 3: Ryan Zeller"

Sarge turns to the Users.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Sometimes it doesn't take a rocket scientist. So which sample came from which glass?

Evans turns the laptop and starts pecking at keys.

EVANS

Interesting thing... One glass had all three fingerprints. The other, just Gerard.

SARGE

So either one of them could have put something in her drink.

(thinks a moment, turns to the Users)

Do you suppose I was a bit hasty in my assumptions back there with that... device?

(to User 2)

Tell me, yes or no: do you think Armova's new love interest... was Gerard?

--option 1--

USER 2

Yes.

SARGE
Yeah... makes sense.

--option 2--

USER 2
No.

SARGE
You sure? Something Zeller said
when we brought him in... about
pillow talk, makes me wonder.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)
Fair to say there were enough
secrets among the three of 'em to
fill a teenage girl's diary.

RACHEL (O.S.)
Sarge? Evans? We found something!

Sarge and Evans look at each other, curious.

SARGE
Let's have a look then.
Sarge leads the group out.
Evans picks up his laptop and tags
along behind.

USER GROUP 2 (WITH RACHEL)-

INT. ARMOVA'S BEDROOM - DAY

Users enter to find Armova sitting on the edge of her bed,
staring longingly at a picture on the bedside table of her,
Gerard and Zeller, all happy and toasting to something.

Rachel looks up from the device.

RACHEL
Ah, good. I've got her settled down
a bit. I think she'll be more
responsive now.
(turning to Armova)
Ms. Armova... won't you tell us who
the new person in your life was...
is? We'd really like to talk to
them.

Armova looks Rachel over, evaluating.

ARMOVA

At least you didn't assume, like
that old dinosaur in there.

Her eyes wander back to the picture.

ARMOVA (CONT'D)

Isn't it obvious?

Rachel follows her eyes, noticing that Armova and Gerard are
arm in arm in the photo.

RACHEL

You mean... Miss Gerard?

ARMOVA

I know she was spying on me... at
first. What Zeller couldn't get out
of me with pillow talk, he paid
Gerard to supply. But his plan
backfired. Christine and I fell in
love.

Something seems to bother Armova... she hesitates.

RACHEL

Was there more to it than that? Did
you ever suspect she was doublecrossing
you both?

Armova overreacts rather dramatically.

ARMOVA

No! Christine would never betray me
like that!

She crosses her arms and turns away, miffed.

Rachel crosses to User 1 and lowers her voice.

RACHEL

Do you think she suspects more than
she's letting on, yes or no?

--option 1--

USER 1

Yes.

RACHEL

Me too.

--option 2--

USER 1

No.

RACHEL

Something about her body language
tells me otherwise.

--both--

RACHEL (CONT'D)

Miss Armova... what were you
celebrating in the picture?

ARMOVA

A major deal with a Greek resort
chain. Christine had only been
working for me for a few months.
She was still on Ryan's payroll,
but the sparks were flying. Late
nights, traveling together... our
first kiss was a few weeks after
this picture was taken. But...

She becomes emotional.

RACHEL

What is it, Miss Armova? You can
tell us. It's very important that
you're completely honest with us.

Starting to cry-

ARMOVA

Everything you need to know is on
the SD card hidden in that picture
frame.

Rachel looks to User 2, nodding toward the picture frame-

RACHEL

Go ahead... see what you can find.

User 2 picks up the picture frame, pulls the back off, and
finds an SD card taped to the back of the picture.

RACHEL (CONT'D)

Sergeant Hoffstetler will want to
see that right away.

Rachel and the Users head back toward the Living Room.

INT. ARMOVA'S LIVING ROOM - DAY

Rachel's group enters the space first, following Rachel.

RACHEL

Sarge? Evans? We found something!
She turns to the User who has the picture frame.

RACHEL (CONT'D)

Go ahead and set that on the table.

The other group enters, led by Sarge. Rachel indicates the frame now lying on the table.

Sarge pulls the SD card off the frame and hands it to Evans, who sits down and puts it into his laptop.

RACHEL (CONT'D)

(to Sarge)

Did you find anything interesting
in the kitchen?

SARGE

You bet. Fingerprints on the wine glasses. Showed Gerard and Zeller both had the opportunity to introduce the poison into Armova's glass. Did you find out who the new lover was?

RACHEL

Gerard... so that could be motive.

EVANS

And so could this.

All attention in the room focuses on Evans as he turns his laptop to face them.

EVANS (CONT'D)

Seems Armova had someone hack into Gerard's bank accounts... she was receiving payments from Zeller every few weeks... up until just last Monday.

RACHEL

She never stopped working for Zeller. If Armova found out... Gerard might have good reason for wanting to keep her quiet.

SARGE

Sounds like we have motive, means
and opportunity, ladies and
gentlemen. Time to bring in Miss
Gerard... in handcuffs this time.

Nods all around.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Nice work, Rachel. Maybe that fancy
piece of technology is worth
something after all.

(to the Users)

And thanks for your help. You're
welcome back any time, as far as
I'm concerned. Good work, everyone.
Someone hit that light switch
again, eh?

He stretches out on the sofa and closes his eyes.

SARGE (CONT'D)

I think I've earned a bit of a kip.

A User hits the switch on the wall, and the lights fade down
to the dim blue they were before, and then all the way to
black.

THE END

ADAPTED SCRIPT DUE TO COVID-19

INT. ARMOVA'S MAYFAIR APARTMENT - LIVING ROOM - DAY

Lights up to find the users inside the meticulously furnished and massive apartment of the late Elena Armova. At a table in the middle of the room find SARGE.

Sarge looks up from his notes, definitely not happy to see the newcomers.

SARGE

Ah... here we go.

He sets his notebook down and stands.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Just for the record, I am not on board with this Civilian Oversight Committee. I have a crime to solve here, now I'm a nanny? Don't expect me to change your nappies, all right?

Sarge points to User One.

SARGE (CONT'D)

While you're here, make yourself useful, it's a bit dark in here. Hit that light switch, would you?

(If they don't:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

The light switch, turn it on.

(If they don't:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

The light switch, on the wall, behind you, turn on the lights!

(When they do:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

There we go, that's better.

User One turns around to find a rocker switch on the wall. When they press it, the lights in the room change.

A young woman, RACHEL (late 20s - early 30s), intellectual, a bit awkward, enters the room carrying a futuristic-looking device.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, Rachel.

(turning to the Users) Everybody,
This is Rachel Tyrell, she's our
Tech Officer. Rachel, this is the Civilian
Oversight Committee I was telling you
about. Rachel is going to install the
AI system that's got everyone in a
frenzy.

RACHEL

Yes... hello.

SARGE

Seems like a lot of nonsense, but
they say since she was such a public
figure, there's enough data to make
it work.

Rachel lays the device down on the table, looks at it and flips a switch. A hologram of ELENA ARMOVA blinks into existence.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Well... that's disconcerting.

Elena, appearing confused and disoriented, looks over at the Sarge, and then around at the apartment.

ELENA

What are you all doing in my home?

Sarge and Rachel look at each other.

SARGE

We just need to ask you a few
questions about last night.

Elena looks around, alarmed.

ELENA

Was there a break-in? Have I been
robbed? I have a very sophisticated
security system.

Elena thinks for a long moment, growing more and more agitated.

ELENA

I... I... don't remember. I... why can't I remember?

SARGE

Just tell us the last thing you do remember then.

ELENA

I... was coming home from a meeting with my board of directors... I was supposed to meet Christine later... Miss Gerard, that is, my assistant. I should call her, she'll be worried..

She starts looking around.

ELENA (CONT'D)

Where's my phone... do you have my phone?

SARGE

We haven't been able to find it. Any idea where you might have left it?

ELENA

I have a phone finder.

She points to a table behind User Four.

ELENA (CONT'D)

If you press the button, it will make the phone ring.

SARGE

Go on, then.

Presumably User Four presses the button.

(If not:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

Go on, press the button.

(If not:)

SARGE (CONT'D)

Press the button on the remote
that's on the cabinet, go on!

(Once they do:) One of the evidence bags on the table begins to
make a really annoying noise.

SARGE

So that's what that is.

SARGE

Look, Ms. Armova, do you have any
reasons to suspect why Christine
Gerard or your boyfriend, Ryan
Zeller, may wish you to do harm?

ELENA

What? Wish me... no, I mean... I was
planning on ending things with Ryan.
I do expect him to be quite upset
when I tell him.

SARGE

What was it, the drugs, the
temper... the industrial espionage?

Elena looks surprised, and a bit offended.

ELENA

No... if you must know. I was
involved with someone else.

Now Sarge is interested.

SARGE

Oh... and who might that be?

ELENA

None of your business, Officer.

SARGE

Look, "Miss", I'm trying to solve
a crime here. I need to get to know
this new fella.

Elena maintains a dignified silence. Sarge looks to Rachel,
annoyed.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Can't you do anything with her?

RACHEL
Like what?

SARGE
Like make her answer!

Rachel shrugs. Sarge shakes his head and steps toward Elena.

SARGE (CONT'D)
Look, Miss... whatever you are.
We're trying to solve a murder
here.

ELENA
A murder? Whose?

SARGE
Yours, sweetheart. So if you could
just answer my questions—

Elena laughs dismissively.

ELENA
That's the most ridiculous
thing I've ever heard. I'm standing
right here talking to you.

SARGE
No, you're not. A hologram programmed to think
it's Elena Armova is standing right here
talking to me, and I don't have time
for the coy games. So if you don't tell me who
the other boyfriend is, I'll turn you
off!

Rachel notices that Elena's hologram
has started to wander away (perhaps add a flicker here as she
gets further away from the projection device?). She quickly
picks up the device and follows Elena.

RACHEL (CONT'D)
Wait, Miss Armova...

She picks up her machine and follows Elena into an adjoining room. Sarge turns to the group, addressing User Five.

SARGE

Well well... you, listen out.
Do you think we'll
get more information about her
new beau out of her?

--option 1--

USER 1

Yes.

SARGE

Well, you're welcome to try then.

--option 2--

USER 1

No.

SARGE

Me neither. Waste of time, if
you ask me.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)

Either way, I'm headed into the
kitchen to do some real police
work. Two groups, two of you
with me, and two of you with Rachel
and her new toy.

Sarge heads in the opposite direction from the two women.

USER GROUP 1 (WITH SARGE) -

INT. ARMOVA'S KITCHEN - DAY

Sarge is already in the kitchen talking with a TECH, who is
examining three glasses by the sink.

SARGE

Two shades?
That's interesting. What are the
chances Armova changed her lipstick
in the middle of the evening?

Sarge looks up to see the USERS.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Ah, there you are. Now you'll get to see some real police work. Young Evans here was just telling me that there are two different shades of lipstick on the glasses. So what, Armova was having a drink with her assistant, perhaps?

The Tech (EVANS) is brushing finger-printing dust on the glasses now and looking them over.

EVANS

And... it looks to me like three different sets of fingerprints, actually.

SARGE

Three? Uh, now we're getting somewhere.

Evans takes a picture of each fingerprint, and the information appears.

SARGE

Don't tell me... Armova, Gerard and Zeller.

The results pop up: "SAMPLE 1: Elena Armova; SAMPLE 2: Christine Gerard; SAMPLE 3: Ryan Zeller"

Sarge turns to the Users.

SARGE (CONT'D)

You see, sometimes you don't have to be a rocket scientist. So which sample came from which glass?

EVANS

Gerard, Zeller and Armova.

The results pop up.

SARGE

So either one of them had a
good opportunity to put
some poison in her drink.

(thinks a moment, turns to
the Users)

Do you suppose I was a bit hasty in
my assumptions back there with
that... device?

(to User 2)

Tell me, yes or no: do you think
Armova's new love interest... was
Gerard?

--option 1--

USER 2

Yes.

SARGE

Yeah... makes sense.

--option 2--

USER 2

No.

SARGE

You sure? Something Zeller said
when we brought him in... about
pillow talk, makes me wonder.

--both--

SARGE (CONT'D)

Fair to say there were enough
secrets between the three of 'em to
fill a teenage girl's diary.

(beat)

But it's not enough to get a conviction,
not yet. I do hope Rachel's group has
something. You two stay, I'm gonna see
what she found.

USER GROUP 2 (WITH RACHEL)-

INT. ARMOVA'S BEDROOM - DAY

Users find Armova sitting on the edge of her bed, staring longingly at a picture on the bedside table of her, Gerard and Zeller, all happy and toasting to something.

RACHEL

Ms. Armova... won't you tell us who the new person in your life was... is? We'd really like to talk to them.

Armova looks Rachel over, evaluating.

ARMOVA

Isn't it obvious?

Rachel follows her eyes, noticing that Armova and Gerard are arm in arm in the photo.

RACHEL

You mean... Miss Gerard?

ARMOVA

I know she was spying on me... at first. What Zeller couldn't get out of me with pillow talk, he paid Gerard to supply. But his plan backfired. Christine and I fell in love.

Something seems to bother Armova... she hesitates.

RACHEL

Was there more to it than that? Did you ever suspect she was doublecrossing you both?

Armova overreacts rather dramatically.

ARMOVA

No! Christine would never betray me like that!

She crosses her arms and turns away, miffed.

Rachel crosses to User 1 and lowers her voice.

RACHEL

Do you think she suspects more than
she's letting on, yes or no?

--option 1--

USER 1

Yes.

RACHEL

Me too.

--option 2--

USER 1

No.

RACHEL

Something about her body language
tells me otherwise.

--both--

RACHEL (CONT'D)

Miss Armova... what were you
celebrating in the picture?

ARMOVA

A major deal with a Greek resort
chain. Christine had only been
working for me for a few months.
She was still on Ryan's payroll,
but the sparks were flying. Late
nights, traveling together... our
first kiss was a few weeks after
this picture was taken. But...

Starting to cry-

ARMOVA

Everything you need to know is on
the SD card hidden in that picture
frame.

Rachel looks to User Two, nodding toward the picture frame. Rachel
takes it.

Rachel picks up the back of the picture frame (the part that has the SD card taped to it) and heads for the door.

RACHEL (CONT'D)

I'll see if Sarge has finished in the kitchen. Wait here for a moment.

INT. ARMOVA'S LIVING ROOM - DAY

The groups arrive in the Living Room together to find Sarge, Rachel waiting for them.

RACHEL

Sarge, we found something here, and you?

She pulls the SD card into his laptop.

SARGE

You bet. Fingerprints on the glasses. Showed Gerard and Zeller both had the opportunity to put poison her. Did you find out who the new lover was?

RACHEL

Gerard... so that could be motive.

All attention in the room focuses on Sarge as he turns his laptop to face them.

EVANS (CONT'D)

Seems Armova had someone hack into Gerard's bank accounts... she was receiving payments from Zeller every few weeks... right up until last Monday.

RACHEL

She never stopped working for Zeller. If Armova found out... Gerard she had a good reason to keep her quiet.

SARGE

Looks like we have, means, motive
and opportunity, ladies and
gentlemen. I think it's time to bring in
Miss Gerard, once again.
This time, in handcuffs.

Nods all around.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Nice work, Rachel. Maybe that fancy
toy of yours is worth
something after all.

(to the Users)

And thanks to all of you. You're
welcome back any time, as far as I'm
concerned. Good job, everyone.

He stretches out and closes his eyes.

SARGE (CONT'D)

I think I've earned a bit of a rest.

SARGE (CONT'D)

Go on then, don't make me change
my mind back again.

(Assuming they do:) A User hits the switch on the wall, and
the lights fade down to the dim blue they were before, and
then all the way to black.

THE END

ANNEX II - CALL FOR FILMING

Films #3, Armava
Ondas de rodaje
Miércoles, 27 de mayo de 2020

Información de contacto
DIRECCIÓN: Ignacio Lacosta, 644 97 65 79
PRODUCCIÓN: Ana Revilla, 639 30 69 94
PRODUCCIÓN: Guillermo Calahorra, 644 05 91 38

HORARIO DE RODAJE: 09:00 - 20:00 LISTOS A LAS: 09:00
LOCALIZACIÓN: C/ Juanes 1 nº3 local, Cuarte de Huerva, 50410

PREVISIÓN METEOROLÓGICA

Wed	Soleado
	Máxima: 30°C
	Mínima: 15°C
30° 16'	Precipitaciones: 0%

Salida actores en Madrid Atocha: 06:20 (Llegada de actores a Madrid Atocha por su cuenta)
Llegada actores a Zaragoza Delicias: 07:44
Taxi en parada de taxi reservado: 07:55 (<https://www.elpais.com/que-es-el-sistema-de-taxis-reservados>). Espes Guillermo C.
Taxi con dirección al estudio de rodaje en C/ Juanes 1 nº3 local, Cuarte de Huerva, 50410 (<https://www.google.com/maps/@41.6750000,-0.8150000,15z>)

En set: 8:45 (no hay maquillaje ni peluquería)
Esaño y lectura de guión: 09:00-13:00
Lunch break: 13:00-14:00 (El Monasterio de Santa Fe, C/ Santa Fe, 14, 50410 Cuarte de Huerva, Zaragoza)
Comida a pedir: <http://www.elmonasteriodesantafe.com/web/index.php/cont-restaurant/>
Rodaje: 14:00-20:00

Taxi con dirección a Estación Delicias desde el estudio de rodaje: 20:00

Hospital:
Hospital MAZ Zaragoza Av. Academia Gral. Militar, 74, 50015 Zaragoza

EQUIPO TÉCNICO		EQUIPO DE ACTORES	
DIRECTOR/DOP	Ignacio Lacosta	ACTOR	Jonathan D. Mellor
PRODUCCIÓN EJECUTIVA	Ana Revilla	ACTRIZ	Aida Ballmann
ASISTENTE DIRECTOR	Guillermo Calahorra	ACTRIZ	Ana Revilla
SUPERVISOR VISUAL MOCA.P	Ignacio Lacosta	ACTOR	Guillermo Calahorra
CÁMARA	Simón Aranda		
TÉCNICO SONIDO	Francisco de Miguel		
GAFER	Simón Aranda Jr.		

CITACIÓN EQUIPO TÉCNICO

DIRECTOR/ DOP	Ignacio Lacosta	08:00	PRODUCCIÓN EJECUTIVA	Ana Revilla	08:00
CÁMARA	Simón Aranda	08:00	PRODUCCIÓN	Guillermo Calahorra	08:00
SONIDO	Francisco de Miguel	08:00	GAFER	Simón Aranda Jr.	08:00

CITACIÓN EQUIPO DE ACTORES

PERSONAJE	ACTOR	ON SET	ENSAYO	RODAJE
Sarge	Jonathan D. Mellor	08:45	09:00	14:00
Elesa Armava	Aida Ballmann	08:45	09:00	14:00
Rachel	Ana Revilla	08:45	09:00	14:00
Evans	Guillermo Calahorra	08:45	09:00	14:00

ESCENAS

ESCENAS	EFECTO	DECORADO	Página	PERSONAJES	LOC.	HORARIO
SEQ 1	INT	LIVING ROOM	1-6	1-SARGE 2-ARMOVA 3-RACHEL	1	TBA
SEQ 2	INT	KITCHEN	6-7	1-SARGE 4-EVANS	1	TBA
SEQ 3	INT	BEDROOM	8-10	2-ARMOVA 3-RACHEL	1	TBA
SEQ 4	INT	LIVING ROOM	10-11	1-SARGE 2-ARMOVA	1	TBA

NOTAS DE PRODUCCIÓN Y DIRECCIÓN

MAQ/PELU/VEST NO HAY. LOS ACTORES VENDRÁN CON ROPA QUE PERMITA VER SUS MOVIMIENTOS

MATERIAL DE DECORACIÓN:

- Cadenillo
- Boligrabo
- Fumante device
- Vaso
- Cámara
- Tableta SD
- Marco de fotos
- Ordenador portátil / fúmsita

PRODUCCIÓN NOTAS: MONTAJE DECORADOS AVANCE:

- 1° Ensayo acting con props + Facial Mocap tests
- 2° Acting shooting + Facial MOCA.P shooting

SEQ 1:

- Lubrica
- Boligrabo
- Fumante device
- Marco de fotografías en la pared

- Marco de Phone finder en la pared
- Evidences log - phone

SEQ 2:

- 3 Vasos
- Cámara
- Cepillo
- Ordenador portátil / fúmsita

SEQ 3:

- Marco de fotos
- Tableta SD
- Fumante device

SEQ 4:

- Marco de fotos
- Tableta SD
- Ordenador portátil / fúmsita

ORDEN DE TRANSPORTE: MAPAS

MADRID ATOCHA A ZARAGOZA DELICIAS

ZARAGOZA DELICIAS A ESTUDIO EN CUARTE DE HUERVA

ESTUDIO EN CUARTE DE HUERVA A RESTAURANTE

ESTUDIO EN CUARTE DE HUERVA A ZARAGOZA DELICIAS

Fig. 48. Call for filming

ANNEX III - GOOD PRACTICES

The Spanish Film Commission published the “Good practice guide for safe shootings”⁵, due to all the questions that arose due to the pandemic situation. In this document, some recommendations and advice is given, to let technical and professional people know how to act and behave during the shooting of an audiovisual piece. The following table shows some of the pages that the production team of TheMo applied to the shooting of the third pilot of the project.

	<p>PRODUCCIONES AUDIOVISUALES EN TIEMPOS DEL COVID-19 RODAJES SEGUROS GUÍA DE BUENAS PRÁCTICAS</p> <p>Normas básicas ⁴</p> <p>Cumplir la normativa de seguridad y salud laboral</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Las condiciones de seguridad y salud en cualquier centro de trabajo que en estas circunstancias tiene permitida su actividad, y para cualquier persona trabajadora en él, deberán cumplir con la normativa de seguridad y salud laboral derivada de la Ley de Prevención de Riesgos Laborales y todos los reales decretos de desarrollo. Además, se deberán cumplir también las medidas definidas por las Autoridades Sanitarias. <p>Actuar ante los primeros indicios y síntomas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Si eres profesional del sector audiovisual y presentas cualquier sintomatología (tos, fiebre, dificultad al respirar...) que pudiera estar asociada con el COVID-19 no debes acudir al trabajo; tienes que contactar con el teléfono de atención de tu Comunidad o con tu centro de atención primaria. No debes reincorporarte a tu actividad hasta que te confirmen que no hay riesgo para ti o para otras personas. Si has estado en contacto estrecho o has compartido espacio sin guardar la distancia mínima establecida con una persona afectada por el COVID-19, tampoco debes acudir a tu puesto de trabajo, incluso en ausencia de síntomas, por un espacio de al menos 14 días. Durante ese periodo tienes que realizar un seguimiento por si aparecieran signos de la enfermedad. Se informará a todo el personal trabajador de que en caso de mostrar sintomatología asociada a la enfermedad del COVID-19 o sospecha de ello, avisen a la empresa y se mantengan en cuarentena en su domicilio, sin acudir presencialmente al puesto de trabajo. Si te encuentras en el puesto de trabajo e identificas muestras de sintomatología asociada a la enfermedad del COVID-19, deberás extremar la precaución y consultar con los servicios sanitarios. Si no fuera posible la asistencia médica, tendrás que permanecer en cuarentena hasta que la autoridad sanitaria determine el procedimiento a seguir.
<p>PRODUCCIONES AUDIOVISUALES EN TIEMPOS DEL COVID-19 RODAJES SEGUROS GUÍA DE BUENAS PRÁCTICAS</p> <p>Antes de un rodaje</p> <p>Plan de Contingencia COVID-19</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Las productoras deberán elaborar y facilitar a trabajadoras y trabajadores un Plan de Contingencia o Protocolo General de Seguridad y Salud Laboral sobre el COVID-19, que recogerá las medidas preventivas y de protección específicas para cada espacio y puesto de trabajo concretos, teniendo en cuenta las condiciones psicofísicas y de salud de las personas que los ocupan. El Plan de Contingencia o Protocolo General de Seguridad y Salud Laboral sobre el COVID-19 deberá ser práctico, sencillo y claro. Estará sometido a seguimiento constante por las empresas y sus trabajadores y trabajadoras en función de la evolución de la enfermedad y las directrices que determinen en cada momento las autoridades sanitarias. La productora aplicará este Plan de Contingencia COVID-19 o Protocolo General de Seguridad y Salud Laboral a todas las actividades que lleve a cabo, así como a las empresas subcontratadas y a todas aquellas que accedan a los espacios de trabajo, set o lugar en el que se rueda. <p>Mutua de Seguros y profesionales PRL o RL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> La productora ofrecerá a todo el personal, en el momento de la incorporación al proyecto, información sobre la mutua de accidentes correspondiente. En el caso de que el trabajo transcurra en diferentes localizaciones, será necesario conocer el hospital (con servicio de urgencias) y la mutua de accidentes más cercana. Corresponde a las productoras, en cada caso concreto y en función de la naturaleza y características del rodaje, evaluar la conveniencia de contar en el set con una persona profesional en el ámbito de la Prevención de Riesgos Laborales, Recursos Preventivos y/o Sanitario. 	<p>PRODUCCIONES AUDIOVISUALES EN TIEMPOS DEL COVID-19 RODAJES SEGUROS GUÍA DE BUENAS PRÁCTICAS</p> <p>Prevención en centros de trabajo y set</p> <p>Distancia Interpersonal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Las tareas y procesos laborales deben planificarse para que las personas puedan mantener la distancia interpersonal de aproximadamente 2 metros, tanto en la entrada y salida como durante la permanencia en el centro de trabajo o set de rodaje. Deben evitarse aglomeraciones de personal en las zonas comunes. Cuando sea posible, se señalará con marcas en el suelo, o mediante el uso de balizas, cartelera y señalización la distancia de seguridad interpersonal mínima. Cuando la naturaleza de la actividad lo permita, se mantendrá la correspondiente distancia interpersonal con terceros, así como el uso de equipos de protección adecuados al nivel de riesgo. Cuando la naturaleza de la actividad no permita respetar la distancia interpersonal, las personas implicadas harán uso de equipos de protección adecuados al nivel de riesgo como medida de protección. Se limitará al mínimo imprescindible el uso de ascensor o montacargas y se utilizarán preferentemente las escaleras. Cuando su uso sea necesario, la ocupación máxima será de una persona, salvo que se garantice la separación de dos metros entre ellas, o en aquellos casos de personas que puedan precisar asistencia. <p>Paneles informativos</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Se deberán instalar en los rodajes elementos de señalización, carteles informativos con medidas de higiene y cualquier otro mensaje que se estime adecuado para garantizar el cumplimiento de las medidas de higiene y prevención frente al COVID-19. La productora colocará estos elementos de señalización, carteles informativos y mensajes en lugares visibles, espacios comunes y baños con las recomendaciones básicas y las propuestas de protección.

Fig. 49. Good practices guide for safe shootings

⁵ <http://www.shootinginpain.info/uploads/files/GUÍA%20BUENAS%20PRÁCTICAS%20ÚLTIMA%20VERSIÓN%20SFC.pdf>

ANNEX IV - SHOOTING AND ACTION LISTS

The following figures illustrate the shooting and action lists that were developed twice, for the expected shooting in Geneva (the first one) and the reduced version for shooting in Zaragoza. The action list was reduced since the script was cut, and half of the actions performed by users were, as well, deleted.

#	ROOM	SEQ	PAGE	WHO	OBJECT 1 / Animated	OBJECT 2 /Static	ACTION	COMMENTS
1	1	1A	1	SARGE	Notebook/Pen/Chair	Table	Taking notes in notebook	Sarge is "cataloguing", he takes notes, doesn't need to touch the evidence bags (which are on the table)
2	1	1A	1	2 Forensics	Evidence bag ?	Table	Walking around	
3	1	1A	1	SARGE	Notebook/Pen/Chair	Table	Putting down the notebook(pen?), Standing, talking to user	We could make all that way easier if Sarge is always standing (no chair) and the notebook stays on the table, he just writes on it...
4	1	1A	1	SARGE		Table	Pointing,Talking to user 1 (light switch)	Fixed feet / We need to know in advance where will be the user in the room and the switch(wall) REPETITION 1
5	1	1B	1	SARGE		Table	Talking to Users (turn it off)	Fixed feet / REPETITION 2 Sarge can move a bit while sayi
6	1	1B	2	SARGE		Table	Talking to User 2	Fixed feet / REPETITION 3A 3B
7	1	1C	2	RACHEL	Futuristic device	Table	Entering in the room and carrying the	Need to know what's the device shape (to create a matchin
8	1	1C	3	RACHEL		Futuristic device/Table	Setting up the device	"Setting up" is vague... Please no cables to plug, only butto
9	1	1C	3	ELENA			Elena appears. Talking	
10	1	1C	3	SARGE	Badge		Shows his badge to Elena	Where is this badge...? And where does it go after? Could t
11	1	1C	3	SARGE	Remote	Table	Sliding across the table to User 3	ALL CHARACTERS Fixed feet REPETITION 4
12	1	1D	3	RACHEL				
13	1	1D	3,4	ELENA			Talking, pointing to charger by the	
14	1	1D	5	SARGE			Talks to User 4	ALL CHARACTERS Fixed feet REPETITION 5
15	1	1E	5	SARGE	Bag with device	Table	Sound. Pressing button	
16	1	1E	5,6,7	ELENA			Stand up / Talking	
17	1	1E	7	RACHEL	Device	Table	Picks the device up, follows Elena	
18	1	1E	8	SARGE			Talks to Users, leaves the room	Fixed feet REPETITION 6, need to know where is the door
19	2	2A	8	SARGE				
20	2	2A	8	EVANS	Wine glasses / Brush	Sink, height ?	Picking up/examining them/brushing	To save time and some props interactions, he is just finishi
21	2	2A	8,9	EVANS	Camera / SD Card	Table	Taking pics/ Pulls out the Card, puts it	this interaction isnt easy...
22	2	2A		EVANS			Talks to User 1	ALL CHARACTERS Fixed feet REPETITION 7
23	2	2B	9	EVANS	Computer	Table	Turning the laptop/ pecking the keys	
24	2	2B	9,10	SARGE			Talking to Users/ leaving the room	ALL CHARACTERS Fixed feet REPETITION 8
25	2	2B	10	EVANS	Computer	Table	Picking it up/ leaving the room	
26	3	3A	10	ELENA	Device	Bed + picture	Sitting, looking at picture	
27	3	3A	10,11	RACHEL			Looks up from the device	Where is the device? Could be on the bed... So that she
28	3	3A	11	RACHEL			Talking to user	ALL CHARACTERS Fixed Feet REPETITION 9
29	3	3B	12	ELENA		Bed + picture	Talking	
30	3	3B	12	RACHEL	Picture frame	Picture	Talking to User 2	ALL CHARACTERS Fixed Feet REPETITION 10 - REPETITIO
31	3	3B	13	RACHEL			Picking up and leaving the room	What happens with Elena? Rachel should switch her off
32	1	4A	13	RACHEL	Picture frame/SD Card		Pulls out card/ Give it to Evans	
33	1	4A	13	EVANS	SD Card/ Computer	Chair/Table	Sitting down/ Pulling the SD car in the	
34	1	4A	14	SARGE		Sofa	Talking to Users/ Stretching on the Sofa	ALL CHARACTERS Fixed Feet REPETITION 12

SEQ	ROOM	PAGE	FILENAME	WHO	TRACKED OBJECT	OBJECT 1 / Animated	OBJECT 2 /Static	COMMENTS
DAY 1 Starting at 2pm								
3A	3	10,11	3A_001	ELENA, RACHEL		Futuristic device, Picture frame	Bed	
3B	3	12,13	3B_001	ELENA, RACHEL		Futuristic device, Picture frame	Bed	
2A 2B	2	8,9,10	2A_001	SARGE, EVANS		Brush, Wine glasses?, Camera, SD Card	Table, Sink (at least right height)	If possible for the actors, shoot 2A-2B continuously
4A	1	13,14	4A_001	RACHEL, EVANS, SARGE	Chair	Picture frame, SD Card, Computer	Table, Sofa	
DAY 2 Starting at 8.30am								
1A 1B	1	1,2	1A_001	SARGE, Forensics(s)	Chair ?	Pen, Chair	Notebook, Table	If possible for the actor, shoot SEQ 1A-1B continuously /if Sarge ca be standing, no need to track the chair
1C 1D	1	2,3,4,5	1C_001	SARGE, RACHEL, ELENA		Futuristic device, Badge, Remote	Table	If possible for the actors, shoot SEQ 1C-1D continuously
1E	1	5,6,7,8	1E_001	SARGE, RACHEL, ELENA		Futuristic device, Bag with alarm device	Table	
DAY 3 Starting at 8.30am								
Overflow from Day 1 and 2 (remaining content)								

Fig. 50 Complete shooting and action lists

#	ROOM	SEQ	PAGE	WHO	OBJECT 1 / Animated	OBJECT 2 /Static	ACTION	COMMENTS
1	1	1	2	SARGE	Notebook/Pen	Table	Looking up his notes in notebook	SARGE Fixed feet REPETITION 1 Device shape (shoebox) : rectangular, simple: 3 buttons Push buttons Light Switch is a mark (color paper) Phone finder is a mark (color paper) ALL CHARACTERS Fixed feet REPETITION 2 SARGE Fixed feet REPETITION 3
2	1	1	2	SARGE			Putting down the notebook(pen?), Standing, talking to user	
3	1	1	2	SARGE			Pointing,Talking to user 1 (light switch)	
4	1	1	3	RACHEL	Futuristic device		Entering in the room and carrying the device, laying it on the table	
5	1	1	3	RACHEL		Table	Setting up the device	
6	1	1	3	ELENA			Elena appears. Talking	
7	1	1	3	RACHEL			Standing	
8	1	1	3,4	ELENA	Phone Finder (on Table behind User4)		Talking / pointing to table behind User4 (phone finder is on the table)	
9	1	1	4	SARGE			Talks to User 4	
10	1	1	5,6	ELENA			Talking / leaves the room to bedroom	
11	1	1	6	RACHEL	Futuristic Device	Table	Picks the device up, follows Elena	
12	1	1	6,7	SARGE			Talks to User 2, leaves the room to kitchen	
13	2	2	7	SARGE				the glass are always standing in the table ALL CHARACTERS Fixed feet REPETITION 4
14	2	2	7,8	EVANS	glasses / Brush	Table	Examining glasses / brushing	
15	2	2	8	EVANS	Camera	Table / Computer	Taking picture	
16	2	2	8,9	SARGE			Talking to User2 / leaving the room	
18	3	3	9	ELENA		Bed /table/ picture	Sitting, looking at picture	Elena entering in the room. Sitting on the bed. Rachel following her ALL CHARACTERS Fixed Feet REPETITION 5 Elena stays in the room (idle)
18	3	3	9	RACHEL	Futuristic Device	Bed		
19	3	3	10	RACHEL			Talking to user 1	
20	3	3	11	RACHEL	Picture frame		Picking up Picture Frame and leaving the room	
21	3	3	11	ELENA				
22	1	4	11	RACHEL	SD Card / Futuristic Laptop		Pulling the SD Card into the laptop	
23	1	4	11,12	SARGE		Sofa	Turning the laptop/Talking to Users/ Stretching on the Sofa	

Fig. 51 Reduced shooting list